

SECOND-CHANCE EDUCATION AMIDST PANDEMIC: REFLECTIVE NARRATIVES OF ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM (ALS) LEARNERS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 4

Pages: 534-566

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2174

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13273335

Manuscript Accepted: 07-27-2024

Second-Chance Education Amidst Pandemic: Reflective Narratives of Alternative Learning System (ALS) Learners

Amillana Z. Kumpa,* Jeannet E. Canda, Geraldine D. Rodriguez

[For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.](#)

Abstract

This study aimed to provide an in-depth exploration of second-chance education during the pandemic, utilizing a qualitative phenomenological research design. Additionally, purposive sampling was used to select the participant in this study. Thus, the research involved 16 Alternative Learning System (ALS) learners, with 8 participants undergoing individual interviews (IDI) and another 8 participating in focused-group discussions (FGD). Three overarching themes—challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights—were formulated to comprehensively capture the experiences of ALS learners. In examining the challenges faced by ALS learners amid the pandemic, several emergent themes emerged, including the difficulties associated with completing modules, adapting to changes, coping with the absence of face-to-face classes, securing access to necessary gadgets, overcoming shyness, dealing with module retrieval, and addressing issues related to poor internet connection. Furthermore, the coping mechanisms employed by ALS learners during the pandemic yielded additional emergent themes. This included fostering confidence, maintaining resilience, cultivating a positive mindset, embracing faith, fostering independence, self-motivation, seeking assistance when needed, and drawing inspiration from family support. The final theme, reflecting on the experiences of ALS learners during the pandemic, revealed insightful emergent themes. These encompassed recognizing the essence of hope, understanding the advantages and disadvantages, discovering personal growth, achieving educational success, emphasizing persistence, acknowledging the significance of effort, recognizing the substantial impact of ALS, advocating for the program, and remaining vigilant in the face of challenges.

Keywords: *educational management, pandemic, second-chance education, alternative learning system*

Introduction

"Never give up on learning, even if you fail; what occurred yesterday no longer concerns today, so get back on track and closer to your goals. Second chance education can help to do so." -Mike Rose

The above statement emphasizes that it is vital to maintain a never-ending commitment to learning, even in the face of failure. By adopting a growth mentality, we can see setbacks as opportunities for improvement rather than deciding to give up. What happened yesterday should not dictate today's actions; each new day provides a chance to start anew and pursue the objectives with renewed vigor. Resilience and determination are vital to staying on track and moving closer to the goals. The journey towards success is rarely without hurdles, but overcoming these challenges helps them grow stronger and wiser. Instead of being disheartened by past failures, we should learn valuable lessons and apply them to our ongoing endeavors.

Notably, the COVID-19 outbreak has severely impacted the educational field, and Alternative Learning Systems (ALS) have become a vital resource for learners who cannot pursue their studies through traditional means. ALS learners, who were already disadvantaged before the pandemic, are now facing additional obstacles in their quest for education. These difficulties include restricted access to resources like electronic devices and the internet, challenges in self-directed learning, and increased stress and anxiety due to pandemic-related uncertainties. It is crucial to comprehend the experiences of ALS learners during the pandemic, as this information can guide decisions on policies and programs aimed at improving their access to quality education. The research results on this subject can be utilized to develop interventions that address the specific needs of ALS learners and minimize the adverse effects of the pandemic on their education (Vatsalawamy, 2020).

In the Philippines, the Alternative Learning System (ALS) is a parallel learning system that gives out-of-school youth and adults (OSYA) learning to read essential and functionally access comparable pathways to finish primary education. Many Filipinos need the opportunity to attend and complete formal primary education (Grades 1-6 and Years 1-4) for various reasons. Some students drop out of school, while others live in areas without schools. Because every Filipino has the right to free primary education, the government established ALS to allow Filipinos to access and complete primary education in a way that suits their unique circumstances and needs (Abad & Galleto, 2020).

Additionally, the law ensures equitable access for all learners, including those living in unreached, underserved, conflict-affected, and emergency-affected communities, to systematic, flexible, and appropriate alternative basic education programs outside the formal school system. It also encourages lifelong learning opportunities based on the ALS K-12 Basic Education Curriculum (BEC), which takes a holistic, integrated, and intersectoral approach and provides pathways across modes of learning to ensure learners become caring, self-reliant, independent, productive, and patriotic citizens by allowing such learners to pursue further education after participating in the ALS program and passing the accreditation and equivalency assessments (Chavez & Tadena, 2021).

Moreover, DepEd Palimbang District I provides second-chance education amidst the pandemic in every barangay of Palimbang District I, Palimbang, Sultan Kudarat. The ALS teachers do their best to deliver and provide quality education using blended learning modality even during the COVID-19 pandemic to ensure the education of the ALS learners in Palimbang District I.

Similarly, the Alternative Learning System (ALS) is a crucial alternative education program that caters to marginalized and out-of-school learners, aiming to provide them with an opportunity to complete their primary education. However, with the sudden onset of the pandemic, traditional face-to-face ALS classes have been disrupted, leading to an urgent need for innovative and adaptable approaches to ensure continued learning for ALS participants. The research gap lies in examining the effectiveness of various remote learning modalities adopted during the pandemic, such as online classes, blended learning, and distance education, specifically tailored to ALS learners' unique needs and circumstances.

Thus, regarding ALS education amidst the pandemic is of utmost importance. With the COVID-19 pandemic disrupting traditional face-to-face ALS classes, there is an immediate need to understand the effectiveness of remote learning modalities, such as online and blended learning, to ensure continuous education for marginalized and out-of-school learners. The urgency lies in identifying the most suitable approaches and overcoming barriers, such as limited access to technology and internet connectivity, to ensure that ALS participants can continue their education without interruption. Additionally, investigating the long-term impacts of the pandemic on ALS education is essential for developing timely interventions and support systems to prevent adverse effects on learners' educational trajectories and well-being.

Nevertheless, research has yet to be conducted to determine the Alternative Learning System learners' challenges, coping, and sharing reflections during this pandemic. It is to be noted that there was a significant decline in the enrolment for ALS for the year 2021-2022. Thus, this context pursues the research to describe the second chance education amidst the pandemic as a reflective narrative of ALS learners in the Palimbang I, Palimbang, and Sultan Kudarat institutions.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the Alternative Learning System (ALS) learners amidst the pandemic. Specifically, this study sought to answer the question:

1. What are the challenges faced by the Alternative Learning System (ALS) amidst the pandemic?
2. How do they cope with their challenges?
3. What are the shared reflections of the Alternative Learning System (ALS) amidst the pandemic?

Methodology

This section presents a description of the research methods and approaches, the role of the researcher, the research participants or population, data collection and analysis, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study employed phenomenological research, a philosophy of experience known as phenomenology. Qualitative research, a unique methodology, is distinguished by its focus on understanding the nuanced and subjective aspects of human experiences and social phenomena. Unlike quantitative design, which relies on numerical data, qualitative research involves collecting non-numerical data through interviews, focus groups, and observations. The emphasis is on exploring the depth, richness, and context of the phenomenon under investigation (Cardano, 2020).

Similarly, qualitative research is a methodology used to understand people's subjective experiences, attitudes, and behaviors by collecting and analyzing non-numerical data, such as text, images, and audio. Thus, this type of research typically involves gathering data through interviews, focus groups, observation, document analysis, and data analysis to identify patterns, themes, and insights (Muzari et al., 2022).

Moreover, qualitative research often seeks to answer open-ended questions that explore complex phenomena, such as social norms, cultural practices, or individual experiences. Qualitative research aims not to measure or test hypotheses but to develop a deep understanding of a particular phenomenon or social context and generate theories or insights that inform further research or practice. Qualitative research is frequently employed in anthropology, sociology, psychology, education, and health care. It is sometimes contrasted with quantitative research, which measures correlations between variables and tests hypotheses using numerical data and statistical analysis (Williams, 2019).

On the other hand, phenomenology is a philosophical approach and methodology that seeks to describe and understand subjective human experiences, perceptions, and consciousness. It emphasizes studying human experience as it is lived and perceived rather than studying objects or events in the external world. Phenomenology focuses on the "phenomena" of experience, which are the subjective qualities or "meanings" that we attribute to objects, events, and situations in the world around us. For example, the experience of seeing a red apple involves not just the physical object but also our perception of its color, shape, texture, and so on (Haven & Van Grootel, 2019; Pearse, 2019).

Additionally, as both a philosophical approach and a research methodology, phenomenology is fundamentally concerned with exploring and elucidating the essence or nature of human experiences. The overarching goal of the phenomenological study is to delve into a person's lived experiences, aiming to comprehend the subjective meanings and structures that define their conscious engagement with the world. Researchers in phenomenology strive to provide a detailed and comprehensive description of these experiences without imposing preconceived theories or interpretations. Essential to the phenomenological process is "bracketing," where researchers temporarily set aside their assumptions and biases to engage with the phenomenon from the participants' perspective (Greening, 2019; Qutoshi, 2018).

Thus, this approach allows for a focused examination of the phenomenon as it is lived, uncovering universal aspects and variations in how individuals experience a particular phenomenon. Phenomenology also contributes to understanding consciousness by exploring the intentional structures through which experiences are organized and given meaning. In essence, phenomenology offers valuable insights into the depth and richness of human consciousness, providing a systematic and rigorous framework for studying the intricacies of subjective experience across various disciplines (Vagle, 2018; Van Manen, 2023).

Similarly, phenomenological research typically involves gathering data through interviews or other inquiry forms and then analyzing the data to identify themes, patterns, and structures in the studied experiences. The goal is to develop a rich and detailed description of the experience being studied and to explore how it is meaningful to the individuals who have it (Errasti-Ibarrondo et al., 2019; Webb & Welsh, 2019).

Likewise, a qualitative research technique, phenomenology, focuses on the commonalities of a group's life experiences. It is essential to construct the universal meaning of the event, scenario, or experience as a result of this approach and get a deeper understanding of the phenomenon. This type of design would determine the challenges Alternative Learning System (ALS) learners face amidst the pandemic. It also gathers reflections and coping ways for ALS learners to address their problems in their studies. The thematic analysis of the gathered data is applied throughout the research process (Umanailo, 2019).

Participants

The participants of this study were the ALS learners of Deped Palimbang District I, Palimbang, Sultan Kudarat. Purposive sampling was employed to determine the study participants. Purposive sampling is a qualitative research technique that identifies and selects information-rich situations to use limited resources efficiently. Thus, it entailed locating and selecting individuals or groups who were particularly educated or experienced about a topic of interest. In addition to knowledge and experience, it emphasized the value of being available, willing to participate, and able to communicate, express, and reflect on ideas and experiences. On the other hand, probabilistic or random sampling was employed to ensure the generalizability of findings by decreasing the possibility of selection bias and controlling for the influence of known and unknown confounders.

In-depth Interviews (IDIs) and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) were employed in this study to gather participant data. The study consisted of sixteen (16) participants divided into two (2) groups, with each group having eight (8) participants. The first group was interviewed using in-depth interview (IDI), and the second used focus group discussion (FGD).

On the other hand, the inclusion criteria for this study were sixteen (16) participants of present Secondary learners within the age bracket of 19-24 years old from the Alternative Learning System of Deped Palimbang District I, Palimbang, Sultan Kudarat, which provides the ALS program. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling method. The participants needed were male or female ALS learners aged 19-24 from DepEd Palimbang District I, Palimbang Sultan Kudarat.

However, the scope of this study was limited to ALS learners. Learners not involved in such a program were excluded from the study. The study focused on learners who were learners of the ALS program, above the age of 18 and under the age of 25. By focusing on ALS learners, this study aimed to achieve a deeper description of the experiences, insights, and challenges faced by ALS learners during the pandemic.

Also, throughout the investigation, it was clear to participants that they were free to leave the study at any time without penalty. Thus, it was essential to ensure that participants were fully informed of their rights and that they felt free to decline an invitation to participate if they felt uncomfortable or unwilling to do so. They were not required to state their reason for withdrawal.

Data Collection

Qualitative research interviews were attempted to reveal the significance and comprehend the universe from the perspective of the subjects of people's experiences and uncover their lived world prior to scientific explanations. Further, qualitative research interviews unfolded as interviewers asked questions of the interviewees to gather subjective information about a particular topic or experience (Quejada & Orale, 2018)

In this qualitative research, the researcher played a central role as the person who collected the data. Regardless of the field of study or preference for defining data as quantitative or qualitative, understanding that accurate data collection was crucial for maintaining the integrity of the research and carefully choosing the appropriate data collection instruments, whether existing, modified, or newly developed, and ensured that it had clear instructions for their correct use. This meticulous approach reduced the likelihood of errors

occurring during the data collection.

Before conducting the study, the researcher asked for permission from the Ethics Research Committee (ERC) to ensure the studies were conducted ethically. Once the committee approved the study, as a researcher, sought permission from the Dean and the Schools District Supervisor of Deped Palimbang District I Pudjia K. Acob, Alhadja, to conduct the study. After obtaining the necessary permissions, it requested collaboration from individuals willing to participate in the study, providing them with an Informed Consent Form. It was crucial that participants understood the study and voluntarily consented to participate. Once participants had given their approval and consent, they could conduct interviews to gather the necessary data for the study. They would ensure the study was conducted ethically and adequately by following these essential steps.

The first eight (8) participants were interviewed using In-depth Interview (IDI), while the remaining eight (8) participants were interviewed using Focus Group Discussion (FGD). The data was obtained during the interviews of the participants, who were interviewed using digital voice recorders, typed transcripts, field notes, and other related materials as the research instruments. After the interview with the participants, the challenges of ALS learners, their coping methods, and reflections were gathered. Transcription was the initial phase in data analysis, entailing close observation of data through repeated diligent listening and watching. Familiarity with data and attention to what was there, rather than what was expected, enabled realizations or ideas to come during the analysis.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was used in this research after the collection of the answers from the participants. Thematic analysis is qualitative data analysis that entails reading over a set of data, such as focus groups or in-depth interview transcripts, and searching for significant trends. Usually, it refers to a collection of texts, such as interview transcripts. Studied the data carefully to uncover recurring themes — subjects, ideas, and patterns of meaning.

Thus, this study uses Colaizzi's data analysis framework for the descriptive analysis. Colaizzi's phenomenological data analysis process has a distinctive seven-step process that provides a rigorous analysis, with each stage staying close to the data. The end product is a succinct yet comprehensive account of the phenomenon under research, supported by its contributors. The method relies on detailed first-person accounts of experience, which can be gathered in various forms, including written narratives, blogs, research diaries, internet interviews, and face-to-face interviews (Praveena & Sasikumar, 2021).

The first step was familiarization. The researcher reads through each participant's account numerous times to become comfortable with the data. Additionally, identifying significant statements is where the researcher identifies all statements in the accounts that directly relate to the phenomenon under investigation.

Moreover, formulating meanings—The researcher identifies meanings relevant to the phenomenon by carefully considering the important assertions. To stay as close to the phenomenon as it is perceived, the researcher must instinctively "bracket" his or her presumptions (though Colaizzi acknowledges that perfect bracketing is never possible).

Furthermore, the fourth step was clustering themes, where the researcher clustered the identified meanings into common themes across all accounts. Presumptions must again be bracketed to avoid any potential influence from existing theory.

Similarly, an exhaustive description was developed, in which the researcher incorporated all the topics generated in step 4 into a comprehensive and all-encompassing account of the phenomena.

Notably, the sixth step was producing the fundamental structure. The researcher reduces the complete explanation to a succinct, dense statement that only includes the elements deemed crucial to the phenomenon's structure.

Likewise, the seventh step was Seeking verification of the fundamental structure, where the researcher returns the fundamental structure statement to all participants (or sometimes a sub-sample in more extensive studies to ask whether it captures their experience. He or she may modify earlier steps in the analysis in light of this feedback.

Thematic analysis might also be carried out in several ways. However, the most well-liked one involves six steps: coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, familiarization, defining and labeling themes, and writing up. The utilized research method is thematic analysis, a versatile psychological research approach applicable to a broad spectrum of studies. This method explores people's perspectives, opinions, knowledge, experiences, and values, identifying recurring themes and patterns in the collected data. The thematic analysis involves six steps, including coding, generating themes, familiarization, reviewing themes, defining and labeling themes, and writing up (Caulfield, 2019). By working collaboratively with a data analyst, they identified and summarized critical statements from participants, facilitating the creation of a comprehensive description of the research field. This process formed the interpretation of the gathered data, aiding in addressing the research questions.

The following methods were used to examine data: Data reduction is the initial stage in analyzing qualitative data. Data reduction entails summarizing, selecting the essentials, focusing on the most significant aspects, and searching for themes and patterns. The second step is to present the data. A display is a condensed, ordered collection of data that allows for conclusion drawing and action.

It was based on formulating the research challenge in reducing and showing the data. Drawing and Verifying Conclusions-Drawing

and verifying conclusions is the third step in qualitative data analysis. The qualitative analysis begins after collecting data, noting regularities, patterns, explanations, alternative configurations, causal processes, and assertions.

Ethical Considerations

For this quantitative study, a critical ethical factor had specific ramifications. These problems and worries can mainly result from the approach used in this study. The ethical considerations in this research concerned the correct conduct of the study, confidentiality, and anonymity. The RMMC Ethics and Review Committee's requirements for ethical consideration were adhered to in this study, especially when it came to the population and data, including but not limited to:

Voluntary Participation. The participants were free to participate without fear of consequences, loss of benefits, or compensation plans. Consequently, when the study's goal and its benefits were conveyed to the participant, their rights to add to the body of knowledge were duly considered and expected. No coercion was used to compel study participants to participate. People have the option to stop participating in the poll if they start to feel uncomfortable.

Privacy and confidentiality. The current Data Privacy Act of 2012, which protects this fundamental human right, states that participants' privacy rights may not be infringed upon without informed consent. One method to protect respondents' privacy and confidentiality in this quantitative study is to allow them to leave their names off of the survey form.

Furthermore, confidentiality and privacy were maintained by not disclosing the informants' age, gender, occupation, or medical conditions. Their identities were kept secret for security purposes. Their responses to the poll were classified as private information and maintained that way.

Informed consent process. Given the investigation's constraints, the possible research participants were suitably educated about the study's objectives, methods, and benefits. The yes answer from the respondents indicates that their participation was requested voluntarily. The essential information about the survey's methodology that participants needed to know was documented in writing. Respondents had to complete an informed consent form attesting to their free will to participate in the study. Since the responders were willing adults; no parental consent was required. The survey form did not reveal the respondents' identity and kept their answers confidential. The study participants were informed that they could discontinue participation at any point.

Furthermore, any data the researcher gathered were protected, and releasing any information would follow a strict informed consent process. The participants would control their personal information to lessen their fear that the data or information would be used in any other unintended manner.

Recruitment. The purpose of the inclusion in the study was explained to the participants. The researcher gave the respondents an explanation of the study's goal so they could draw further conclusions and see the main points of the investigation. In addition to the letter, the researcher explained the study's significance and reasoning.

Risks. Research shall be done if there is an appropriate positive benefit-risk ratio. It is equally essential that the participants in this study are shielded from severe injury. The respondents' welfare was given priority in the study. The responders were also unharmed because their identities were kept private. Their safety and security were the top priorities. As the researcher, ensuring the respondents were psychologically, physically, and socially prepared is a must. In response to the survey, the researcher attested that the participants had neither uneasiness nor discomfort.

Benefits. Second-chance education amid the pandemic serves as a vital avenue for advancing Sustainable Development Goal #4, Quality Education, by addressing the educational disruptions caused by the global health crisis. Though flexible learning modalities such as blended and distance education, second-chance education programs ensure that individuals who may have missed out on traditional schooling opportunities can still access quality education. By leveraging various technologies and innovative teaching methods, these programs empower learners to acquire essential skills, knowledge, and values, promoting inclusivity and lifelong learning. Additionally, second-chance education contributes to mitigating the socioeconomic impacts of the pandemic by providing marginalized persons with the opportunity to enhance their economic prospects and participate meaningfully in society. Thus, amidst the challenges posed by the pandemic, second-chance education emerges as a crucial tool for advancing SDG #4 and building a more equitable and sustainable future.

Plagiarism. There was no hint or proof that the study had misinterpreted someone else's work. Turnitin and Grammarly software, among other plagiarism detectors, will be applied to the study. Equity and good character are essential for researchers and are linked to moral principles and beliefs. The researcher must be more knowledgeable about plagiarism to produce a respectable research report.

Fabrication. The report did not hint or provide evidence that the work had been intentionally misinterpreted. There was no fabrication of information or findings or deliberate presentation of incorrect conclusions. The investigator utilized and incorporated ideas associated with the data and other inferential notions.

Falsification. There was no indication that the study overstated or exaggerated anything, nor did it deliberately falsify the data to meet a model or theoretical expectation. Therefore, this study did not adhere to data manipulation practices, which include making claims, omitting crucial information, or utilizing supplies, equipment, or techniques in a way that could deceive others.

Conflict of Interest (COI). There were indications of a conflict of interest in the study, such as COI disclosure or situations requiring expert opinion on the main appeal. A conflict of interest tends to affect the welfare of participants or the quality of the research and is comparable to financial academic advantages or recognitions. Such conflicts can compromise the objectivity of the research findings and undermine the trust in the study's outcomes. Ensuring that any potential conflicts are disclosed and managed appropriately is essential to maintain the integrity of the research process. Furthermore, the researcher, who had no authority or influence over the respondents, forced them to take part in the survey. This coercion raises serious ethical concerns, as it violates the principle of voluntary participation.

Deceit. The study did not indicate that the participants were misled about any potential risk. The rights of participants in any study must be enormously protected, particularly if they have completed higher education; therefore, reasonable and acceptable guidelines must be followed. Furthermore, ensuring transparency and obtaining informed consent are crucial to maintaining ethical standards. Researchers should also be vigilant in providing accurate information about potential risks and benefits. Upholding these principles not only respects participants but also enhances the credibility and reliability of the research.

Permission from Organization/Location. The study's researcher adhered to protocol. The researcher formally requested permission from the superintendents of the Schools Division to perform the study by letter after getting the signal from the panelists, the adviser, and the committee of the RMMCERC. Following this, the researcher composed an official letter and attached the school's letter of support from the school division's superintendent to the District Supervisor and Principal of the participating schools in the study. Before giving out the survey questionnaire, the ALS students involved in the study received orientation. Additionally, the researcher ensured all ethical considerations were met by obtaining informed consent from all participants.

Results

This qualitative phenomenological study aimed to learn more about the participants' challenges, coping mechanisms, and reflection amidst the pandemic. The outcomes interviews were also given in this study. Each participant was disguised under a pseudonym to protect the chosen instances' identities and privacy.

Description of Participants

This study consists of sixteen (16) participants. Eight (8) participants were interviewed using IDI; the second group was FGD.

IDI-Participant 1- Alex, a 19-year-old secondary learner, a diligent learner, and a student in the ALS program of Palimbang, Sultan Kudarat.

IDI-Participant 2: Bailey, a 20-year-old secondary learner, is a motivated learner who constantly seeks knowledge and actively engages in discussions.

IDI-Participant 3: Casey, a 21-year-old learner, is articulate and open-minded. She is part of the ALS program.

IDI-Participant 4- Dylan, a 22-year-old secondary and a reflective and introspective learner of the ALS program.

IDI-Participant 5- Erin, aged 23, is a passionate and expressive participant with a strong sense of enthusiasm and dedication.

IDI-Participant 6—Finn, a 24-year-old secondary learner, is insightful and offers a unique perspective as an older participant in the ALS program.

IDI-Participant 7- Grace, a 20-year-old, thoughtful, wise participant and a learner of the ALS program.

IDI-Participant 8- Hayden, aged 21, is an active and engaged learner and a secondary learner in the ALS program in Palimbang, Sultan Kudarat.

FGD-Participant 1: Jordan, a 19-year-old secondary learner, is an attentive and analytical participant who carefully listens to others' perspectives.

FGD-Participant 2- Morgan, a 20-year-old participant, a self-reflective and introspective learner, provides deep insights into their personal experiences.

FGD-Participant 3—Riley, 21, is an empathetic, compassionate participant and a secondary learner enrolled in the ALS program.

FGD-Participant 4- Avery, a 22-year-old secondary learner, is detail-oriented, articulate, well-structured, and thoughtful.

FGD-Participant 5- Parker, aged 23, participated in the Alternative Learning System conducted in Palimbang, Sultan Kudarat.

FGD-Participant 6- Taylor, a 24-year-old secondary matured learner, provides a seasoned perspective as an older participant in the ALS program.

FGD-Participant 7- Cameron, aged 20, is an insightful and observant participant, offering valuable observations and reflections based on their experiences.

FGD-Participant 8—Sydney, a 21-year-old secondary learner, is a curious and analytical participant who asks probing questions and offers analytical insights.

Categorization of Data

This part presents the analysis of themes through data categorization, including the challenges, coping, and reflection of ALS students amidst the pandemic.

3.1. The Challenges of ALS Students Amidst the Pandemic

Table 1 presents the challenges of ALS students during the pandemic and depicts the selection criteria as identified. This study discusses seven challenges. The table describes the essential themes gathered about ALS students' challenges amidst the pandemic. Moreover, core ideas are presented based on the responses of participants.

Table 1. *The Challenges of ALS Students Amidst the Pandemic*

<i>Cluster Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Find it hard to answer the modules. Difficulties in understanding the activities found in the modules. Preferred teachers to explain the lessons in the modules. Cannot understand the questions in the module.	Answering the modules
Find the new everyday learning quite challenging. Find it hard to adjust to the pandemic. Find adjusting hard due to a lack of instructional materials. Difficulties getting the modules due to transportation problems. Better for them if there had been a face-to-face class. Used to face-to-face classes.	Adjustment Absence of face-to-face classes
Found it hard to answer the modules alone. Struggle with the absence of the teacher. Felt behind with the information given by the school due to the lack of gadget. Need to learn how to use innovative gadgets. Find it difficult to answer online activities because their gadget cannot be used for research.	Gadget
Find shy about being left behind by their classmates. Felt too shy to enroll because of their age. Were shy.	Shyness
Felt thankful because they were given a chance to continue with their studies. Find it hard to get the modules at school due to health issues. Have difficulties in retrieving the modules because they live in a far-flung area. Retrieving modules was hard. No transportation was available. Felt sad whenever they could get the modules. Need a better internet connection, which leads them to fail to do the same tasks. Cannot connect to the internet.	Retrieval of Module Poor Internet Connection
They need an unstable internet, which hinders them from attending online classes. Failed to be updated because they do not have an internet connection.	

Answering the Module. One of the challenges the participants encountered during the pandemic was the struggle to answer modules because they needed help understanding the lessons. Eight of the participants had the same sentiment. The modules were challenging for them to complete. The activities included in the courses could have been more apparent to some. If the teacher had explained the teachings in the modules, it would have been better for them. They needed help understanding the module's questions.

“Ang mga hamon ng mga estudyante panahon ng pandemya ay ang pagmomodules at online classes ngunit Kailangan nating mag aaral online class man o modules ay gawin natin ang lahat ng ating makakaya kahit hindi tayo face to face classes.” (IDI Participant 1, lines 8-11)

Students face challenges during the pandemic, including taking modules and online classes. However, we students must do everything we can, whether online or in modules, even if we do not have face-to-face classes.

“Mahirap ang module dahil minsan mayroon akong hindi mahintindihan sa module at walang makapag explain sa akin. Mas madali kapag face to face dahil andyan ang aming guro upang makagabay at makatulong sa amin” (IDI Participant 3, lines 194-197)

The module is complex because sometimes we need help understanding something or explaining it to someone. It is easier to communicate face-to-face because our teacher is there to guide and help us.

“Ang hamon na aking naranasan ay noong akala Kong Hindi ko makaya ang mga Gawain at exercises at hindi ko matuto.” (IDI Participant 3, lines 225-226)

The challenge experienced was when we thought we could not handle the tasks and exercises and could not learn.

“Kahirapan, dahil karamihan sa amin nahihirapan sa pagsagot ng module.” (IDI Participant 4, lines 279-280)

Complicated because most of us need help in answering the module.

“Hindi ko maintindihan ang mga tanong sa module kaya nahihirapan din akong sagutan ang mga ito.” (IDI Participant 5, lines 439-440)

We need help understanding the questions in the module, and we need help answering them, too.

“Nahihirapan akong intindihin ang mga tanong sa modules.” (IDI Participant 7, lines 627)

We have to answer the sheet or modules without the teacher explaining them.

“Ang masama kong karanasan ay nahihirapan ako minsan sagotin ang mga modules ko lalo na kapag Hindi ko maintindihan.” (FGD Participant 4, lines 315-317)

The bad experience is the need for help to answer the modules, especially when understanding.

“Ang masaya at malungkot kong mga sandali bilang ALS learner sa bagong normal na edukasyong ito ay dahil sa ako ay nakapag -aral kahit na modular lamang ay may natutunan naman ako ngaunit mas makabubuti sana kung face -to -face class dahil mas maunawaan mo ang itinuturo ng guro Hindi katulad sa modular na Hindi mo masyado nauunawaan ang mga lesson.” (FGD Participant 5, lines 432-436)

We were happy and sad moments as an ALS learner in this new normal of education because we could study even though it was only modular. We learned something, but it would have been better if it was a face-to-face class because we would better understand what the teacher is teaching; unlike modular, we need help understanding the lessons.

They are happy asking other people for answers but sad because they ask people to help them answer their modules. Even with the mobile teacher's explanation, their minds are still wandering, and they need help knowing how to answer questions and what to do. (FGD Participant 7, lines 619-622)

Adjustment. Five participants struggled with this challenge due to the need for instructional materials. Learning the new normal took much work for them. They had trouble adjusting to the pandemic. Due to a shortage of instructional materials, they needed help to adjust.

“Ang masaya at malungkot na mga sandali bilang als ay isang pagbabalik ng bagong normal na edokasyong ito para sa panibagong pag babalik aral ng mga mag aaral pero ito ay pagkasakali pa lang dipa ayos ang lahat.” (IDI Participant 1, lines 28-30)

The happy and sad moments as an ALS student are a return to this new average education for students to return to school again, but this is after everything is in order.

“Mahirap ngunit dapat na tiisin kahit ang katumbas nito’y hindi ko na palagi kasama ang aking mga kaibigan sa ALS dahil ito’y para rin sa aming kaligtasan.” (IDI Participant 2, lines 157-159)

It is hard but must be endured even if it is worth it. Not always be with ALS friends because it is also for safety.

“Sa new normal education, nahihirapan ako mag adjust dahil na rin siguro sa kakulangan sa gamit.” (IDI Participant 5, lines 389-390).”

Had difficulty adjusting to the new average education, probably because of the need for more equipment.

“Ang naging hamon ng ALS sa amin bilang isang mag-aaral noong wala pang COVID-19 ay parati kaming magkakasama ngayon na may COVID-19 ay hindi na pwede magtabi-tabi kasi po kailangan po natin maging maingat.” (FGD Participant 6, lines 568-569)

When COVID-19 was absent, the challenge that ALS posed to us as students was that we were always together. Now that COVID-19 is present, we can no longer be side by side because we must be careful.

“Mahirap pag sabayin ang pag aaral habang nagtaratarabaho ng gawain pang bahay.” (FGD Participant 6, 532-533)

It is hard to combine studying with doing housework.

“Nanibago lang po sa mga pangyayari at sa bagong sistema. Sa una nanibago palang ako pero nang nakaraan ang ilan araw nakasanayan kuna ang sestema ng ALS.” (FGD Participant 8, lines 681-682)

It just changed with the circumstances and the new system. At first, we changed, but after a few days, the ALS system got used to it.

“Ang mabuting karanasan ko ay mas natututo akong paano pahalagahan ang bagay-bagay na nasa paligid natin ang masama kung naranasan ay ang pag adjust ko ng aking oras sa bahay at sa pag aaral ng ALS.” (FGD Participant 8, 685-687)

We excellent experience was learning to appreciate the things around us. Our lousy experience was adjusting our time at home and studying ALS.

Absence of Face-to-Face Classes. Seven participants preferred face-to-face classes, finding it challenging to comprehend lessons without immediate assistance during the pandemic. Participant 1 expressed that the pandemic significantly altered their educational experience, making it less effective despite the lessons learned and the personal growth it fostered. Other participants highlighted the discouragement from pursuing dreams, the absence of readily available teachers, and the lack of peer support as significant barriers to their learning, with some even unable to pass due to restrictions on leaving their homes.

“Ang masamang karanasan ko sa panahon ng pandemya malaki ang pinagbago ng pagkuha ko ng edukasyon at Hindi ito ang dati Kung kasanayan at ang mabuti kong karanasan natututo ako sa maraming bagay at naging hamon sa buhay ko.” (IDI Participant 1, lines 18-21)

The bad experience during the pandemic changed us a lot when we got an education; it is not what it used to be. If we are used to it and our good experience, we learn many things, which has been a life challenge.

“Nakakaapekto ito sa aking pag aaral dahil napang hinaan ako ng loob patungo sa aking mga pangarap sa buhay.” (IDI Participant 3, lines 251-252)

It affects our studies because it discourages us from pursuing our dreams.

“Ang kawalan ng guro na agad malapitan.” (IDI Participant 6, line 441)

The absence of a teacher who is immediately close.

“Walang pwedeng tumulong sa akin pag di ko alam.” (IDI Participant 8, line 603)

Help someone who does not know.

“Hindi na ako makahingi ng tulong sa mga kaklase ko.” (IDI Participant 7, line 523)

No longer ask classmates for help.

“Mahirap dahil walang guro na gumagabay sa amin upang marami kaming matutunan.” (FGD Participant 1, lines 3-4)

It is difficult because there is no teacher to guide us so that we can learn a lot.

“Bilang ALS learner naranasan ko po na hindi makapasa dahil po sa pandemya kasi po bawal lumabas ng bahay o barangay.” (FGD Participant 6, lines 526-527)

As an ALS learner, we experienced not being able to pass because of the pandemic because we were not allowed to leave the house or barangay.

Lack of Gadget. The lack of gadgets meant a lack of updates/information received from the school. Two of the participants faced this problem. Due to a lack of equipment, they fell behind in the information provided by the school. They were unable to use cutting-edge technology. Since their devices could not be utilized for research, they found it challenging to respond to online activities.

“Ang hindi pagkasabay sa information about sa school dahil walang connection or kawalan ng cellphone. Minsan nahihirapan sa pagsagot ng module.” (IDI Participant 4, lines 283)

Not keeping up with information about the school because there is no connection or lack of a cellphone. Sometimes, there is difficulty in answering the module.

“Ang hindi maka sabay o maka update about sa school dahil sa pandemya o kawalan ng cellphone.” (IDI Participant 4, lines 309-310)

Not being able to stay together or update about school because of the pandemic or the lack of cellphones.

“Ang mga challenges na naharap ko ay ang kawalan ng cellphone at signal. Hindi rin ako marunong gumamit ng mga bagay na pangsearch.” (IDI Participant 5, lines 362-363)

The challenges I faced were the need for cell phones and signals. We also needed to learn how to use the search bar and applications.

Shyness. Participants frequently encountered shyness, often feeling embarrassed about being left behind by their classmates, which led to their reluctant enrollment. Despite their initial hesitation, they felt grateful for the opportunity to continue their education. This chance allowed them to overcome their shyness and pursue their dreams.

“Hiya, dahil ang ibang classmate ko ay they moving up. Pero may pangarap ako to make future to continue. As an ALS learning they give me a chance to improve.” (IDI Participant 4, 285-287)

Shy because other classmates are moving up. However, having a dream to make a future is why we want to continue. As ALS learners, they give us a chance to improve.

“Medyo nahihya at naexcite.” (IDI Participant 5, line 369)

Shy and excited.

“Nahihya pero ngayon, laking pasasalamat ko sa Panginoon.” (IDI Participant 6, line 447)

Shy, but now, very thankful to the Lord.

Retrieval of Module. The retrieval of modules posed a significant challenge for participants during the pandemic due to strict protocols and limited transportation. With fewer public vehicles available, many found collecting and submitting their modules difficult, often resorting to walking long distances. One participant shared the difficulty of needing a motorbike to ride, making it hard to leave the house to get the modules. Another expressed sadness over not being able to see ALS colleagues regularly and the struggle of walking to obtain the modules. This sentiment was echoed by several participants, who felt frustrated and disheartened by the obstacles they faced in continuing their education.

“Ang hamon na aking naranasan sa ALS sa gitna ng pandemya ay ang limitadong labas ng bahay kaya nahirapan ako magkuha ng modyul dahil walang nagabiyahe na motor para masakyan.” (IDI Participant 2, lines 95-97)

The challenge I experienced with ALS during the pandemic was limited outside of the house, so getting a module was difficult because there was no traveling motorbike to ride.

“Naranasan ko bilang ALS learner na hindi masyadong makakuha ng modyul dahil sa pandemic.” (FGD Participant 1, lines 7-8)

Experienced as an ALS learner, unable to get many modules due to the pandemic. As ALS learners, we could not get much of the module because of the pandemic.

“Malungkot po ako kapag hindi ako makakuha ng module lalo na kapag wala akong sasakyan para mag kuha or mag pasa.” (FGD Participant 6, lines 540-541)

We were sad when we could not get our modules, especially when we could not get a ride to get or send them.

“Ang naging hamon sa akin dahil sa malayo ang aking bahay mensan hindi ako maka pasa ng module lalo na kapag wala akong masakyan.” (FGD Participant 6, lines 568-569).

It was a challenge because the house was so far away that we could not pass the module, especially when we did not have a ride.

Poor Internet Connection. Poor internet connection was a significant challenge for three participants, hindering their ability to complete tasks and attend online classes. Their erratic internet access made it difficult to keep up with school information and answer modules. One participant mentioned the frustration of not having a reliable connection or a cellphone, which added to the difficulty. This issue and other pandemic-related disruptions greatly affected their ability to adapt to the new learning system.

“Ang hindi pagkasabay sa information about sa school dahil walang connection or kawalan ng cellphone. Minsan nahihirapan sa pagsagot ng module.” (IDI Participant 4, lines 283)

Not keeping up with information about the school because there is no connection or lack of a cellphone. Sometimes, there is difficulty in answering the module.

“Sa tingin ko, ang mga hamon na aming kinaharap bilang pag-aaral ng ALS noong panahon ng pandemya ay katulad ng mga disturbo at mahinang koneksyon sa internet para sa mga online klase at ang limitadong paggalaw ay mga natukoy na hamon na naranasan sa pambansang antas.” (FGD Participant 3, lines 202-204)

The challenges we encountered as ALS learners during the pandemic, such as interruptions, poor internet connections for online classes, and limited movement, were identified as challenges experienced on the national level.

“Para sa akin noong nagka pandemya ay labis tayong naapektuhan sapagkat bilang estudyante mahirap makipag sapalaran sa bagong sistema ng pag-aaral nariyan na ang mabagal na internet connection distrakyon at mga gawaing bahay. ngunit huwag tayo mawalan ng pag asa babalik din tayo sa nakasanayan, kakayanin ko ang lahat para sa pangarap.” (FGD Participant 5, lines 479-483)

When the pandemic happened, we were greatly affected because, as students, it was challenging to deal with the new learning system; there was a slow internet connection, distractions, and housework. We should do what we can to fulfill our dreams.

3.2. The Coping Mechanism of ALS Students

Table 2 shows ALS students' coping mechanisms with their challenges. Based on participants' responses, the table discusses eight coping mechanisms, along with their core ideas.

Table 2. *The Coping Mechanisms of ALS Students with the Challenges They Have Encountered*

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Dealt with the challenges wholeheartedly.	
Handle the challenges encountered confidently and peacefully.	Being Confident
Make parents inspired to deal confidently with the challenges.	
Confidently faced the challenges to continue living.	
The form in facing the challenges brought on by the pandemic.	
Kept on being brave no matter how complex the challenges are.	Being Firm and Strong
Stay firm for them to face all the difficulties.	
Stand still to achieve dreams.	
Be positive because everything happens for a reason.	
Be positive and behave that this will be surpass all the challenges.	Thinking positively
Have a positive outlook in life in order to survive.	
Keep on believing in things successfully and to be able to face all the challenges of the pandemic.	
Prayer and determination helped to go forward amidst the pandemic.	
Keep on having faith.	Having Faith
Cope with the challenges with the help of other people.	
The essence of being independent in answering their modules.	
Learned to stand alone and fight for dreams.	Being Independent
Independently face all the challenges by believing in the potential.	
Very responsible in doing school-related and household choices.	
Keep on motivating themselves to survive.	
Doing best to achieve the dreams.	Motivating Oneself
Believed that the ALS program would help them eradicate poverty.	
Keep on finding ourselves to help our family after graduation.	
Asked for help whenever they could not answer the module.	
Felt happy asking for help from others.	Asking for Help
Asked for help to understand the module better.	
Asked for help from siblings, cousins, classmates and parents.	
Strive hard to surpass the challenges because of the family.	
Doing best to face the challenges because of family.	
The family served as inspiration not to give up.	Making Family an Inspiration
Love for family become an inspiration to cope up with the challenges.	

Being Confident. The participants admitted that being confident in facing the challenges was one of their coping mechanisms for surviving the new normal of education amidst the pandemic.

“Hinarap namin ng buong puso ang bawat hamon dahil sa paniniwalang lahat ay may katapusan at ito’y isang pagsubok lamang na dapat lagpasan.” (IDI Participant 2, lines 123-125)

We face every challenge wholeheartedly because we believe everything has an end and is just a test to overcome.

“Harapin ko ang mga hamon sa buhay ng may tatag na loob at pananalig sa panginoon ano mang pagsubok sa buhay ay makakayanan ko dahil inspirasyon ko ang aking mga magulang at dahil sa tulong ng ating panginoon ay makakayanan ko ang lahat para makamit ang pangarap ko sa buhay.” (IDI Participant 3, lines 219-222)

As students, we will face the challenge with a positive outlook, believing we can graduate. We will trust in ourselves, and especially in God.

“Haharapin namin ang hamon sa amin upang kami ay magtagumpay sa aming mga pangarap at hindi hadlang angkahirapan upang kami ay suko sa hamon ng buhay.” (FGD Participant 2, lines 124-126)

We will face the challenges of succeeding in our dreams and not being hindered by poverty so that we surrender to life's challenges.

“Bilang isang mag-aaral haharapin ko kung ano man ang hamon sa akin upang ako ay magtagumpay sa aking sarili. Hindi naman hadlang ang kahirapan upang ako ay hindi magpatuloy sa aking pag-aaral. Haharapin ko aking karanasan upang maabot ko ang aking pangarap at hindi ito maging hadlang upang ako magpatuloy na tahakin ang aking mga pangarap sa buhay.” (FGD Participant 2, lines 128-130, 137-139)

As students, we face whatever challenges we face to succeed. Poverty is not an obstacle for us not to continue our studies. Face the experiences to reach our dreams and not let them become obstacles so that we can continue to follow them.

“Haharapin ko ang aking mga hamon na naranasan ng may malawak na pasensiya, at matatag na kaisipan sapagkat lahat ng pagsubok ay dumadaan lamang.” (FGD Participant 3, lines 239-241)

Face the challenges with great patience and a strong mind because all trials are passing.

“Harapin ko ang aking mga hamon bilang isang mag-aaral upang ako ay matuto sa mga bagay-bagay at magkaroon ng magandang kinabukasan sa hinaharap.” (FGD Participant 5, lines 442-445)

Face the challenges as a student to learn from things and have a bright future.

Being Firm and Strong. The participants acknowledged that they had to be firm to accomplish everything they set out to do for their future.

“Kailangan maging aktibo at maging matatag sa bawat kinakaharap sa buhay.” (IDI Participant 1, lines 45-46)

Need to be active and be strong in every face of life.

“Kinailangan kong pagtibayin ang aking sarili para sa aking pangarap at magandang kinabukasan sa tulong ng ALS walang imposible.” (IDI Participant 2, lines 135-136)

Affirm the dream and bright future with the help of ALS. Nothing is impossible.

“Nagkatatag ako sa lahat ng hamon na dumarating sa aking buhay upang ako ay magtagumpay sa lahat ng gusto kong marating.” (IDI Participant 3, lines 243-244)

We must be strong in all the challenges that come in life to succeed in everything we want to achieve.

“Dahil po sa hirap ng buhay kailangan ko magpatuloy sa buhay at magpakatatag para sa aking mga pangarap.” (IDI Participant 5, lines 403-404)

Because of life's hardships, we should continue to move forward and be vital to achieving our dreams.

“Kailangan nilang maging matatag at masipag bilang isang mag-aaral.” (FGD Participant 1, lines 26-27)

They need to be solid and diligent as a student.

“Masasabi ko na mahirap ang pagbabago dahil ngayon ko lamang ito naranasan bilang ALS learner. Ang aking lakas ng loob ang aking ginagamit para harapin ang hamon at problema ko kapag gusto may paraan pag ayaw maraming dahilan mas maganda din ang may tiwala ka sa sarili mo bilang mag-aaral.” (FGD Participant 4, lines 349-351)

Change is difficult because of the inexperience in ALS. So, use courage to face challenges and problems. There is a way when we want and many reasons if we do not. It is also better to have confidence as a student.

“Ang payo na aking maibibigay sa ibang mag-aaral ng ALS na katulad ko ay huway silang sumuko sa kanilang hamon bagkos kanila itong haharapin at magpatuloy sa buhay para matupad ang kanilang pangarap at magkaroon na magandang kinabukasan sa hinaharap.” (FGD Participant 5, lines 503-506)

The advice I can give to other ALS students is that they should not give up on their challenge but face it and continue in life to fulfill their dreams and have a bright future.

“Harapin ko ito Na may tibay loob at tapang na May kalmadong pag-iisip.” (FGD Participant 8, lines 700-701)

Face it with courage and courage with a calm mind.

Thinking Positively. The participants firmly believed that everything occurred for a purpose. They repeatedly told themselves to remain upbeat and confident in overcoming all obstacles. They had to maintain an optimistic mindset to live. They continued to believe they could accomplish their goals and handle the pandemic's problems.

“Naging positibo sa lahat nang nangyayari palaging isipin na ang lahat ng nangyayari ay may dahilan makakabuti para sa atin.” (IDI Participant 1, lines 41-42)

Be positive in everything that happens. Always think that everything that happens has a reason that will be good for us.

“Ang pagiging positive sa lahat upang ipagpatupad ang pagpapahatid ng ALS.” (IDI Participant 4, lines 330-331)

Be positive in everything when implementing the delivery of ALS.

“Bilang isang mag-aaral, haharapin ko ang hamon ng may positibong pananaw na makakapagtapos din ako. Tiwala sa sarili at lalong lao na sa Diyos.” (IDI Participant 5, lines 385-386)

As students, we will face challenges with a positive outlook, believing we can graduate. Trust in ourselves, and especially in

God.

“Laging nakatatak sa aking isip na magtatapos ako ano mang mangyari at dahil duon, nakakaya kong harapin ang bawat hamon sa buhay bilang isang mag-aaral.” (IDI Participant 5, lines 393-395)

I always knew I would graduate no matter what, and because of that, I was prepared to face every challenge in life as a student.

“Kahirapan ang nag-uudyok sa akin para magpatuloy sa aking pag-aaral, at sa paniniwalang balang araw kapag makatapos ako ng aking pag-aaral ay maiaahon ko sa hirap ang aking pamilya at mabigyan sila ng masaganang pamumuhay.” (FGD Participant 1, lines 43-46)

Hardship motivates us to continue our studies. One day, when I finish, I will be able to lift my family out of poverty and give them a prosperous life.

“May mga challenge tayong kinakaharap sa buhay pero bilang isang tao, palaging sinusubukan nating maging positibo.” (FGD Participant 3, lines 231-232).”

We have encountered many challenges in life, but we always try our best to be optimistic.

“Para sa akin huwag tayo sumuko kahit ano paman ang dumating na hamon sa ating buhay bagkos ito ay ating haharapin para malutas ito at magkaroon ng magandang buhay o kinabukasan.” (FGD Participant 5, lines 438-440)

Let us not give up no matter what challenge comes in our lives; we will face it to solve it and have a good life or future.

“Tinatanggap ko ang mga hamon nang buong puso dahil naniniwala ako na kung may tiyaga, may paraan.” (FGD Participant 7, lines 635-636)

We accept the challenges with the heart because there is a way if there is a will.

Having Faith. The participants persevered throughout the pandemic with the help of prayer and willpower. They continued to have faith and believed that they could overcome life's obstacles. The participants overcame their obstacles with assistance from those who shared their optimism.

“Pray at determinasyon na kaya kong abutin ang aking mga pangarap.” (IDI Participant 2, lines 153-154)

Prayer and determination are what we need to reach our dreams.

“Harapin ko ang mga hamon sa buhay ng may tatag na loob at pananalig sa panginoon anumang pagsubok sa buhay ay makakayanan ko dahil inspirasyon ko ang aking mga magulang at dahil sa tulong ng ating panginoon ay makakayanan ko ang lahat para makamit ang pangarap ko sa buhay.” (IDI Participant 3, lines 219-222)

We will face life's challenges with determination and faith in the Lord. I can handle any challenge because our parents inspire us, and because of the help of our Lord, I can handle everything to achieve our dreams.

“Sa tulong ng ating may kapal siya lang po at ang aking pamilya ang ginagamit kong inspirasyon upang lahat ng hamon ay aking natagumpay at may lakas ng loob.” (IDI Participant 3, lines 234-236)

With the help of our may kapal, he and our family are the only inspirations I use to overcome all challenges and have courage.

“Dasal lang talaga sa tulong ng Diyos at ng aking pamilya, sila ang ginagamit kong inspirasyon upang lahat ng hamon ay aking matagumpay at may lakas ng loob.” (IDI Participant 5, lines 398-400)

It is just a prayer. With the help of God and family, they inspire us so that all challenges can thrive and have courage.

“Kahit sa panahon ng pandemya pinipilit ko paren mag Aral dahil para din ito sa aking sarili dahil pandemya kalang malampasan din ito.” (FGD participant 6, lines 564-565)

Even during the pandemic, one must study because it is also for us. After all, it is a pandemic to overcome it, too.

Just pray to God or Allah always, and everything will be all right. (FGD Participant 7, line 624)

Being Independent. The participants recognized the importance of being competent in completing their assignments. They knew how to stand together and pursue their goals. Independently, they overcame every obstacle by having faith in their capacity. They were also highly responsible for their duties, including education and housework.

“Bilang mag aaral sa panahong ito mapapanatili ko ang dignidad sa aking pag aaral sa pamamagitan na pagsusumikap na magkaroon ng mahusay na kaalaman at karunungan sa aking mga gawain sa paaralan.” (IDI Participant 1, lines 53-55)

As students, we must maintain the dignity of studying by striving to have good knowledge and wisdom in school activities.

“Nakakatulong ang aking mga karanasan sa aking kakayahan na gawin ang mga pang araw araw na gawain sa tahanan at

paaralan bilang paghahanda sa aking kinabukasan ano man ang nakaatang sa akin na mga gawain o trabaho ay makakayanan ko dahil nakasanayan ko ang mga gawain sa loob at labas ng tahanan at paaralan.” (IDI Participant 3, lines 206-210)

The experiences help us to prepare for the future by doing daily activities at home and school. Home and school.

“Naranasan ko bilang ALS learner sa new normal education na matuto kahit walang guro na gumagabay sa akin. Bilang isang mag-aaral kailangan kong matuto upang ako’y hindi mahirapan sa ano mang gagawin ko na pagpapasya.” (FGD Participant 1, lines 32-33, 74-75)

The ALS learner's experience during the new average education is to learn even without a teacher to guide them. As students, they have to learn, so they do not easily decide.

“Kailangan mong pag-aralan at sagutin ang iyong mga module kahit hindi mo alam kung paano ito sagutin.” (FGD Participant 7, lines 604-605)

We must study and answer the modules even if we do not know how to answer them.

“Nakakaya ko kung paano i handle ang aking oras sa pag aaral at sa mga gawain o sa mga trabaho ko sa bahay.” (FGD participant 8, lines 690-691)

Managing time spent studying, doing tasks, or working at home.

Motivating Oneself. The participants remained motivated because they believed they could consistently achieve their goals and live life if they completed their ALS education. They were happy as ALS learners because their dream's door had opened again. Therefore, they were inspired to carry on and pursue their dreams. This renewed sense of purpose fueled their dedication and resilience in overcoming challenges. The support from their peers and mentors further strengthened their commitment to their educational journey. As they progressed, they gained confidence in their ability to create a better future for themselves and their communities.

“Ang magandang dulot ng ALS sa akin ay naglalayong makapagbigay ng panibagong pag-asa ng nag manais na makapag tapos ng pag-aaral.” (IDI Participant 1, lines 49-50)

The good thing this has brought is that it gives hope to those who want to finish their studies.

“Gagawin ko ang lahat para maabot ko ang aking mga pangarap sa buhay.” (IDI Participant 2, lines 149-150)

Do everything to achieve one's dream in life.

“Minomotivate ko ang aking sarili para sa mga pangarap ko sa buhay at kailangan kong magpatuloy kahit ano mang hamon na aking maranasan.” (IDI Participant 3, lines 247-248)

Motivate oneself to achieve dreams and keep going no matter what challenges one encounters.

“Napapanatili ko ang aking motibasyon sa pag-aaral dahil sawa na ako sa hirap at kapag nakatapos ako sa aking pag-aaral gaganda na ang aking buhay kasama ang aking pamilya.” (FGD participant 1, lines 49-51)

Maintain motivation to study to relieve hardships, finish the studies, and improve family life.

“Dahil sa pangarap kaya ko napanatili ang aking motibasyon para magtagumpay kahit sa panahon ng pandemya.” (FGD Participant 2, lines 154-155)

Because of the dream, maintaining one's motivation to succeed even during the pandemic.

“Mahirap mag-aral nang walang paliwanag kung paano gawin ito, ngunit alam ko na kaya kong gawin ito. Panatilihin ko ang aking motivasyon dahil ang aking pamilya ay laging nandyan upang suportahan ako.” (FGD Participant 7, lines 647-648)

It is challenging to study without instructions, but knowing we can do it helps us stay motivated. The family's support is also helpful.

Asking for Help. Participants struggled with their modules and sought help from various sources to cope. They frequently asked close friends or classmates who were also studying in the ALS program, and when that was insufficient, they visited the learning center to consult their ALS teacher. Some learners also relied on family members for assistance, though this sometimes left them feeling uncertain without the teacher's explanations, despite appreciating the support they received.

“Kapag hindi Nila Alam ang sagot sa module ay pwede silang magtanong sa kanilang malapit na kaibigan o di kayay Ka klase na nag aaral din sa ALS kung Hindi sila matutulungan ay pwede din silang pumunta sa learning center para magtanong sa kanilang guro sa ALS.” (FGD participant 4, lines 330-333)

When they do not know the answer to the module, they can ask their close friends or classmates who are also studying ALS. If they cannot be helped, they can also go to the learning center to ask their ALS teacher.

“Magtatanong ako sa mga ka klase ko kapag hindi ko alam ang module ko o di kayay pupunta ako sa aking guro para itatanong

ang mga hindi kopa alam.” (FGD Participant 4, lines 335-337)

Ask classmates to help answer the modules or go to the teacher to ask things they do not know.

“Ang hamon na naranasan ko bilang ALS learner sa new normal education ito ay medyo nahihirapan ako dahil may mga words o salita na hindi ko masyado naiintindihan kaya minsan ako ay nagpapatulong sa aking mga pinsan.” (FGD Participant 5, lines 447-449)

The challenge experienced as an ALS learner in New Normal Education is a small quantity of difficulty because there are words that are hard to understand, so sometimes, asking for help from cousins is needed.

“Masaya dahil nakakakuha ako ng mga sagot sa pamamagitan ng pakiusap sa ibang tao, at malungkot dahil humihingi lang ako ng tulong sa ibang tao upang sagutin ang aking mga module. Nang walang paliwanag mula sa aking mobile teacher, ang aking isip ay patuloy na nagtatanong at hindi alam kung paano sagutin at ano ang gagawin.” (FGD Participant 7, lines 619-622)

They are happy because they can get their answers by asking for favors from others, but they are also sad because they ask people to help them answer their modules. Despite all the explanations from their mobile teacher, their minds are still wandering, and they need to figure out how to answer and what to do.

Making Family an Inspiration. Many participants drew inspiration from their families to persevere and complete their education. They worked diligently to achieve their personal goals and lift their families from poverty. As one learner expressed, they strived to improve and succeed in helping their parents and providing a better future for their siblings, driven by a desire to alleviate their family's hardships through the Alternative Learning System (ALS).

“Bilang isang mag-aaral kailangan kong pagbutihin para ako naman ay makatulong ng mabuti sa aking mga magulang at makaraos sa hirap ng buhay. (FGD Participant 1, lines 71-72).”

As a learner, improvement is needed in helping parents cope with life's hardships.

“Ito ang nagiging dahilan upang ako ay magpatuloy dahil ayaw kong maranasan ng mga kapatid ko kung gaano ito kahirap. Gusto ko matulungan ang aking mga magulang at pamilya dahil sila ang dahilan para ako ay magpatuloy sa pamamagitan ng ALS. (FGD Participant 2, lines 162-164).”

Keep going without wanting the siblings to experience how hard it is. Help parents and family because they are the reason to keep going through ALS.

“Ang aking pangarap bilang Alternative Learning System (ALS) learner ay makatapos po ako sa aking pag-aaral at mabigyan ko ng magandang kinabukasan ang aking pamilya at saka makabawi naman ako sa aking mga magulang. (FGD Participant 2, lines 191-194).”

The dream of an Alternative Learning System (ALS) learner is to finish their studies, give their family a promising future, and then make up for their parents.

“Ang aking pamilya, mahirap lang kami at wala kaming sapat na pera upang mabili ang lahat ng pangangailangan ng aming mga anak. Kaya naman, nagpasya akong mag-aral sa ALS upang bigyan sila ng mas magandang kinabukasan at makabili ng lahat ng gusto nila. (FGD Participant 7, lines 642-644).”

Poverty in the family and lacking money to buy the children's needs. So, the decision to study in ALS is to give them a better future and to buy everything they like.

3.3. The Reflections of ALS Students Amidst Pandemic

Table 3 presents the ten essential themes of ALS students' reflections on the pandemic. These included the essence of hope, giving value and identifying advantages, self-growth discovery, achieving educational success, being persistent and vigilant, understanding that effort matters, the significant impact of ALS, and promoting ALS. The table also discussed the students' core ideas. Additionally, it highlighted how these themes reflect the students' resilience and adaptability during challenging times. It further illustrated the profound ways in which the ALS program has influenced their personal and academic growth.

Table 3. *The Reflections of ALS Students Amidst Pandemic*

<i>Clustered Themes</i>	<i>Emergent Themes</i>
Believed that there was hope amidst the pandemic.	Essence of Hope
Brought so much hope to the students amidst the pandemic.	
Hope to finish study amidst the pandemic.	
Have realized that ALS is an avenue for them to achieve their dreams.	
Believed that nothing was impossible in achieving dreams amidst the pandemic.	
Advised other students that there is hoped to be successful because of ALS.	

They are thrilled to study again, and they are full of hope.	
Able to value the advantages of ALS despite studying in the new everyday learning.	
Feel very happy to study at ALS.	
Able to study and, at the same time, work at home.	Value Advantages
Felt grateful that they could continue their studies because of ALS.	
Felt privileged to answer the modules.	
Felt sad because they could not continue their studies because of the pandemic.	
Worried because nobody could teach them the lessons.	Identify Disadvantages
Have learned that studying alone is not easy.	
Still feel sad because misunderstanding the lesson.	
Have discovered that this can help students continue with their study.	Self Growth Discovery
Found out that they can do so much better when it comes to study.	
Have learned to take care of their health more.	
Eager to pursue their dreams amidst the pandemic.	
Realized that they wanted to have a brighter future.	Achieve Educational Success
Have learned to value their education more.	
Doing their best to answer the modules to finish their studies.	
Wanting to graduate and become successful in getting a better job and salary.	
Have realized that being persistent is necessary.	
Believed that persistence and hard work would help surpass the challenges brought on by the pandemic.	Be Persistent
Realized that being persistent will help handle difficulties.	
Value persistence to be a successful person.	
Have learned to be persistent in answering modules amidst the pandemic.	
Believing in giving the best in everything during this pandemic is essential.	Effort Matters
Realized that making the best effort is immense help in facing any challenges amidst the pandemic.	
Have valued the ALS more during this pandemic.	
Very thankful to the Alternative Learning System for the chance to continue studying.	Great Impact of ALS
Believed that ALS was an avenue to dream and learn again.	
Realization of doing much more because of the ALS.	
Doing best to promote the ALS.	
Realized that ALS can help more students.	Promote ALS
Encourage other students to study ALS because it is beneficial.	
Have learned to be more vigilant.	
Believe that health is wealth, so it is essential to be careful.	Be Vigilant
Have realized the value of proper health protocol.	

Essence of Hope. The participants thought that despite the pandemic, there was still hope. In the middle of the pandemic, the ALS gave the kids great optimism. They believed they would be able to complete their education despite the pandemic. The students had come to understand that ALS was a way to fulfill their aspirations. They believed the epidemic would not prevent them from completing their education and achieving success. Despite the pandemic, they believed that nothing was impossible to do. They advised the other students that success was still possible despite ALS. The ALS students were overjoyed to be back in class and were optimistic.

“Bilang isang mag-aaral sa panahon ng pandemya masasabi ko na hindi ito maging isang hadlang sa aking pangarap na kaya ko palang maging maparaan upang patuloy na mabuhay para sa aking kinabukasan na gusto kong mapaganda kasama ang aking mga mahal sa buhay.” (IDI Participant 2, lines 173-176)

As a student during the pandemic, it will not be an obstacle to their dream of being resourceful and continuing to live for their future, which they want to make beautiful with their loved ones.

“Bilang mag aaral ng ALS marami akong natutuhan at napatunayan sa aking sarili na walang impossible sa lahat ng bagay kapag ito ay ginusto mo.” (IDI Participant 3, lines 264-265)

As an ALS student, learning a lot and proved that nothing is impossible in everything if a person wants it.

“Hinihikayat ko yung mga kabataan magpatuloy sa pag-aaral sa ALS, at sa mga kapwa ko mag-aaral ng ALS ipagpatuloy lang po natin ito walang imposible sa taong may pangarap.” (FGD Participant 2, lines 181-183)

Encouraging young people to continue studying ALS. To our fellow ALS students, let us keep doing it. Nothing is impossible for a person with a dream.

I have encountered many happy moments as an ALS learner in this new standard, seeing things back to normal and experiencing going back to school in face-to-face mode again. (FGD Participant 3, lines 220-223)

The happy moments I have encountered as an ALS learner in this new normal are seeing things back to normal and experiencing going back to school in face-to-face modalities again.

“Na feel ko po na may pag-asa sa ALS para makapag-aral ulit.” (FGD Participant 6, line 529)

There is hope that ALS students will be able to study again.

“Ang makapag aral muli at maipagpatuloy, magandang karanansan na iyon. Wala akong maisip na masamang karanansan.” (Participant 7, lines 531-532)

Being able to study again and continue is a good experience. We must think of a good experience.

“Ang aking kwento sa aking pag-aaral sa ALS na ito ay sinabihan ako ng aking mga mababait na magulang na mag-aral para matupad ko aking pangarap. Nakinig naman ako sa kanila kasi alam kong makakabuti din naman sa akin.” (FGD Participant 3, lines 248-251)

The story of an ALS education is that kind parents told us to study to fulfill our dreams. Listening to them because it would be good for the future.

Value Advantages. Despite engaging in the new typical learning environment, the students appreciated the benefits of ALS. They were overjoyed to study at ALS, where they were allowed to work from home while also studying. They were appreciative that ALS allowed them to complete their education. The ALS students considered it an opportunity to submit the modules. This flexibility helped them balance their personal responsibilities and academic work more effectively. Moreover, the support and resources provided by ALS facilitated a more manageable and fulfilling learning experience. As a result, many students felt a renewed sense of accomplishment and motivation to succeed.

“Ang masaya na sandali ko bilang ALS learner ay hawak ko ang oras kasama ng aking pamilya habang nag-aaral. Malungkot naman dahil hindi ko na palagi nakikita ang mga kasamahan ko sa ALS.” (Participant 2, lines 119-121)

The happiest moment as an ALS learner is spending time with the family while studying. It is sad because we cannot see our ALS colleagues all the time anymore.

“Ang masaya sandali na aking naranasan ay noong marami akong natutunan bilang ALS learners at nagagamit ko ito sa pang araw araw.” (Participant 3, lines 213-214)

The happy moment we experienced was the overload of learning as ALS learners, and we can use it daily.

“Sa tulong ng aking karanasan, ako ay handa na para sa kinabukasan.” (Participant 5, lines 376-377)

Readiness for the future is the help of experiences.

“Ang mabuting karanasan ko ay ipagpatuloy ko ang aking pag-aaral sa ALS na nahinto noon.” (FGD participant 2, lines 107-109)

To continue studying ALS, which was stopped before, was a good experience.

“Para sa akin hindi hadlang ang pandemya sa aking pag-aaral kasi ang ALS ay pwedeng sa bahay ka lang at nakakasama mo pa ang iyong mga pamilya.” (FGD Participant 4, lines 300-302)

As a learner, the pandemic is not an obstacle to study because ALS can be done at home, and we can still be with our family.

Identify Disadvantages. Some ALS students experienced sadness since they had to stop their studies due to the pandemic. They were concerned since nobody could impart lessons to them. They now realized how challenging studying by themselves could be. They had learned that teachers' assistance was crucial to learning, yet face-to-face instruction was not an option. Even though they answered the modules, some students still felt disappointed since they needed to grasp the course thoroughly.

“Nagkakaroon ng di maayos na pag-aaral gaya nalang ng pagtigil ng aking pag-aaral sa eskuwela dahil sa pandemya ng ito na dumudulot ng malubhang sakit na maaari nating ikakamatay.” (IDI Participant 1, lines 63-65)

There was a lousy education, like when we stopped studying at school because of this pandemic that causes a severe disease that can kill us.

“Ang kawalan ng alam sa pandemya, dahil tulad namin ALS learners kailangan naming ng guide para sa pinag-aaralan. Ang pagiging tamad kasi may araw na tinatamad ako minsan hindi kuna ma answeran ang aking module dahil dito.” (IDI Participant 4, lines 337-338, 334-335)

The lack of knowledge about the pandemic. Like us, ALS learners, we need a guide for what we are studying. We are lazy because there are days when we are lazy and sometimes do not finish the module.

“Hirap na pag answer ng modules at kapag ito ay hindi ko maintindihin at walang guro na makapag gabay sa amin na mag-aaral.” (IDI Participant 5, lines 421-422)

It is difficult to answer the modules, and when it is, the a need to help in understanding, and no teacher can guide us students.

“Hirap na pag answer ng modules at kapag ito ay hindi ko maintindihin at walang guro na makapag gabay sa amin na mag-aaral.” (IDI Participant 6, lines 500-501)

Answering the modules is complex; when it is, we need help understanding, and no teacher can guide us as learners.

“Nagrereflect ito sa tuwing naaalala ko ang buhay naming noon wala pang pandemya. Kaya sobrang hirap naapektuhan ang aming kabuhayan at pag-aaral naming magkapatid.” (FGD Participant 2, lines 165-167)

It reflects every time I remember our life before the pandemic. That is why our livelihood and siblings' studies were very hard affected.

“Ang aking masamang karanasan naman ay kaunti lamang po kaming nag-aaral ng ALS. Then my sad moments, I think is that we are not still free from the COVID-19 pandemic here in the Philippines.” (FGD Participant 3, lines 222-223)

The limited learning of ALS is considered a bad experience. Sadly, we are still inaccessible due to the COVID-19 pandemic here in the Philippines.

“Para sa akin mas maganda din ang face-to-face kasi makakasama ko pa ang mga bago kong kaibigan at mas maiinspired ako na makita ko ang mga bago kong ka klase at para mas makilala ko sila.” (FGD Participant 4, lines 325-328)

Face-to-face is also better because we can meet new people, become friends, and be more inspired to see new people. If we are classmates, we can get to know them better.

“Masaya ako dahil nakakakuha ako ng mga sagot mula sa mga tao at nakakakuha ako ng mas mataas na marka, ngunit ang masama ay hindi ako masyadong natututo nang mabuti dahil umaasa lamang ako sa iba.” (FGD Participant 7, lines 610-612)

Happy because we can ask people's answers and get a higher grade, but the bad thing is that we cannot learn so well because we depend on others.

Self-Growth Discovery. The participants found they could encourage individuals who desired to continue their education. They discovered that they were capable of doing much better in the classroom. Even though there was a pandemic, the students took an active and proactive approach to answering their modules. They also now knew how important it was to maintain their health.

“Ang pagkatuklas ko sa paraang pandemya nagkaroon ako ng mabuti at madaming aral at naging aktibo at naging madiskarte ako sa paraang kayong pandemya.” (IDI Participant 1, lines 77-79).

The pandemic method taught us many suitable lessons, and we became active and strategic.

“Ang aking natuklasan o natutunan ay ang kalusugan ay kayamanan na siyang isang sandata upang marating natin ang ating mga pangarap sa buhay.” (IDI Participant 2, lines 170-171)

Discovered or learned that health is wealth, a weapon to reach our dreams.

“Natutuklasan ko po ang aking ibang mga kakayahan noong panahon ng pandemya at ito ay nagamit ko sa pang araw araw na gawain.” (IDI Participant 3, lines 261-171)

Discovering other abilities during the pandemic and using them in daily work.

“Natutuklasan ko po ang aking ibang mga kakayahan noong panahon ng pandemya at ito ay nagamit ko sa pang araw-araw na gawain.” (IDI Participant 5, lines 425-46)

Discovering other abilities during the pandemic and using them in daily work.

“Bilang mag-aaral ng ALS marami akong natutuhan at napatunayan sa aking sarili na walang impossible sa lahat ng bagay.”(Participant 5, lines 428-429).”

As ALS learners, we learned a lot and proved that nothing is impossible in everything.

“Ang mga pagkatuto na natuklasan at nakuha ko bilang isang mag-aaral sa panahong ito ng pandemya ay natuto ako magbasa maliban lang sa English dahil medyo mahina ako magbasa ng English.” (FGD Participant 5, lines 496-498)

As students during this pandemic, we made many learning discoveries. We learned to read everything except English because we were weak in reading English.

“Ito ay tumutulong sa akin na lumaki at maging mas responsable sa paggawa ng trabaho sa bahay at paaralan.” (FGD participant 7, lines 615-616)

It helped us grow up and become more responsible for the work at home and school.

Achieve Educational Success. Despite the pandemic, the participants remained keen to follow their aspirations. They realized that they

wanted a better future. They now place a higher priority on education. They have discovered the importance of studying diligently to succeed. They are working as hard as possible to complete the modules to graduate. They want to graduate and succeed in obtaining a higher position and pay.

“Mag-aral ng mabuti at gawin lahat ng pinapagawa ng iyong magandang buhay.” (IDI Participant 1, lines 84-85)

Study hard and do everything for the good life that tells us to do.

“Para ang lahat ng mga kabataan ay makatapos ng pag-aaral upang matulungan nila ang kanilang mga magulang at ang kanilang mga sarili.” (IDI Participant 6, lines 496-497)

So that all young people can finish school and help their parents and themselves.

“Mag-aral at matuto ang out-of-school youth and adults sa pamamagitan ng blended learning na matagal nang ginagamit sa ALS bago pa magkaroon ng pandemya.” (IDI Participant 8, lines 676-678)

Out-of-school youth and adults study and learn through blended learning, which was used extensively in ALS before the pandemic.

“Ang masayang sandali ko bilang mag-aaral ng Alternative Learning System (ALS) ay ang maipagpatuloy ang aking pag-aaral at maaari ko ng maabot ang aking pangarap sa gitna ng pandemya at makabagong panahon ng education.” (FGD Participant 2, lines 118-120)

The happy moment as a student of the Alternative Learning System (ALS) is that we can continue our studies and reach our dreams in the middle of the pandemic and the modern era of education.

“Para sa akin ang aking pag-asa at adhikain pangarap bilang ALS learner ay makapagtapos ng pag-aaral at magkaroon ng magandang trabaho sa hinaharap upang makatulong sa aking pamilya para maging maginhawa ang aming pamumuhay at maihaon sa kahirapan ang aking pamilya.” (FGD Participant 5, lines 515-518)

The hope and dream of ALS learners are to graduate and have an excellent job in the future so that we can help our families, make our lives comfortable, and free them from poverty.

“Pangarap kong mkapasa dahil gusto kong makamit ang aking pangarap.” (FGD Participant 6, lines 596-597)

Dream to pass because of wanting to achieve the dream.

“Talagang kailangan kong ituloy ang aking pag-aaral lalo na ngayong panahon ng pandemya. Mahirap humanap ng trabaho na may magandang sahod o honoraryo. Nais kong tapusin ang aking pag-aaral at magkaroon ng magandang trabaho na may mas mataas na sahod para sa aking pamilya.” (FGD Participant 7, lines 662-663, 672).

Pursuing studies is necessary, especially during the pandemic. Finding a good salary or an honorarium job takes much work. To finish one's studies, one must have an excellent job with a better salary for the family.

Be Persistent. Participants now understand the value of perseverance. They were convinced that their ability to persevere and work hard would enable them to overcome the difficulties of the pandemic. The participants understood that perseverance would enable them to overcome their challenges. Because they desire to succeed in life, the participants place a high priority on perseverance. Despite the pandemic, they have learned to be persistent when answering their modules.

“Natutunan ko ang pagiging matatag sa gitna ng pandemya.” (IDI Participant 4, line 345)

Learned to be resilient amid the pandemic.

“Kailangan nating magpakatatag para sa sarili at para sa pamilya.” (IDI Participant 5, line 431)

We need to be strong for ourselves and the family.

“Maging pursigedo upang ito ay magamit sa lahat ng pagsubok na hamon sa buhay.” (IDI Participant 8, lines 672-673)

Be persistent so that it can be used in all the trying challenges of life.

“Kailangan maging matatag at masipag sa pag-aaral. Kailangan ko maging matatag dahil lahat ng pagsubok ay may katapusan.” (FGD Participant 1, lines 29, 36-37)

Must be assertive and diligent in learning and be strong because all trials have an end.

“Sa pamamagitan ng pagtiis sa kahirapan. Bilang isang mag-aaral kailangan magtiis para makamit lahat ng gustong pangarap sa buhay.” (FGD Participant 6, lines 543-546)

To endure poverty. As a student, one must endure to achieve all desired dreams.

“Payo ko sa kanila na kailangan nila maging matatag para din sa amin lahat ng ginagawa nila.” (FGD Participant 6, lines, 589-590)

Advise them that they must be vital for us and everything they do.

“Huwag kang sumuko, mag-aral ka nang mabuti, at makikita mo na sulit ito.” (FGD Participant 7, line 667)

Do not give up. Just study hard and see if it is worth it.

Effort Matters. The participants believed that putting their all into everything they accomplished was crucial during this pandemic. They understood that staying still would only fail. They had learned that effort counted, and if they worked hard, they could accomplish more. Because of the pandemic, they tried their best to study and work simultaneously. They understood that making the best possible effort would help them overcome any difficulties posed by the pandemic.

“Gawin lahat ng makakaya at laging magtiwala balang araw matutupad mo lahat ng gusto mong marating ng iyong buhay o pangarap.” (IDI Participant 1, lines 88-89)

We should always do our best and believe that one day we will achieve everything we want to in our lives or dreams.

“Para sa akin tinutukoy ako ng pag-aaral sa ALS bilang isang tao dahil ako ay patuloy na nag-aaral sa kabila ng pandemya sa ating isip.” (IDI Participant 8, lines 669-670)

Studying ALS defines us as a person because we continue to study despite the pandemic in our minds.

“Nang dahil sa pandemic nagawa ko pagsabayin ang pag-aaral, mga gawaing bahay, at makatulong sa aking mga magulang sa hanap buhay. Hindi naging hadlang ang pandemic para sa aking mga pangarap, at mapagsabay ang pag-aaral sa mga gawain sa aming tahanan.” (FGD Participant 2, lines 112-115)

Because of the pandemic, combining studies with housework and helping parents earn a living has not been an obstacle to reaching our dreams, and studies can go hand in hand with our household chores.

“Ibinahagi ng mga estudyante ng ALS ngayong pandemya ay ang pakikipagtulungan sa bawat isa.” (FGD Participant 2, lines 170-171)

What ALS students share during this pandemic is working together with each other.

“As a learner, I think we need to do the multitask since humaharap kami sa maraming hamon sa buhay na mag tetest sa aming capabilities bilang tao.” (FGD Participant 3, lines 216-217)

As learners, we must multitask since we face many life challenges that test our capabilities.

“Ang aking diskarte sa aking pag-aaral ay mag-aaral ako ng mabuti ng sa ganoon ay makatapos ako at magkaroon ng trabaho para hindi na kami makaranas ng hirap.” (FGD Participant 3, lines 243-245)

The strategy for studying is to study hard so that we can finish and get a job so that we do not have to suffer anymore.

“Sa laban na ito ang ating mga pagsusumikap at palakasan ay naka ang kala sa paglilingkod sa kapwa Pilipino at ang pagtitiyak sa kaligtasan ng ating mga mag-aaral.” (FGD Participant 4, lines 379-381)

In this battle, our efforts and sports are focused on serving our fellow Filipinos and ensuring the safety of our students.

“Harapin nila ang kanilang mga hamon sa pamamaraan ng kanilang pagsusumikap na ma sulusyonan ang kanilang hinaharap naproblema sa kanilang buhay.” (FGD participant 8, lines 697-698)

They face their challenges in the way they strive to solve their future problems in their lives.

“Dapat maging masipag lamang at laging mag iingat sa ano mang mga kilos na ating gagawain.” (FGD participant 8, lines 378-379)

We must be diligent and always be careful in whatever actions we do.

Significant Impact of ALS. During the pandemic, participants appreciated ALS more. They appreciated that the Alternative Learning System had allowed them to complete their education. The participants felt that many pupils benefited from the ALS program, particularly those who could no longer study. They thought that ALS allowed them to dream and study again. They also understood that ALS had allowed them to accomplish so much more.

“Pangarap kong matutunan ang aralin sa ALS at higit sa lahat po ay pangarap kong makapasa ng ALS. Dahil sa ALS nakabalik ako ulit sa aking pag aaral.” (IDI Participant 1, lines 91-92)

The dream of learning in ALS and of passing it. Also, because of ALS, we can continue our studies.

“ALS ay daan ng pag-asa para sa mga pangarap ng mga taong minsan naligaw na tulad ko.” (IDI Participant 3, lines 272-273)

ALS is a path of hope for the dreams of people like us who once lost their way. We only wish to achieve our dreams with the help of ALS.

“Dahil sa ALS binigyan ako ng pag-asa kaya gusto ko pa ang maging isang mabuting mag-aaral sa aking sarili sa ALS Program dahil dito kulang nakikita ang pag asa.” (IDI Participant 4, lines 354-356)

Because of ALS, hope was given, and wanting to be a good learner in the ALS Program because hope is here.

“Dahil sa ALS natutuhan kong maging masipag sa aking pag-aaral.” (FGD Participant 1, line 81)

Learned to be diligent because of ALS.

“Ang aking mabuting karanasan bilang isang mag-aaral na natututo sa ALS ay natuto ako sa maraming bagay tulad ng pagbasa sa dati ay hindi ko masyado alam. Ang masamang karanasan ko naman bilang isang mag-aaral na natututo sa ALS at yun ay kung paano umintindi sa mga salita tulad ng English sapagkat wala ako masyadong kaalaman sa mga salitang English lalong-lalo na kung ano ang ibig sabihin nito.” (FGD Participant 5, lines 420-426)

Our good experience as students learning ALS is that we learned many things, like reading, that we did not know much about before. Our lousy experience is understanding words like English because we need to learn more about English words, especially what they mean.

“Narealize ko po na meron pang pag-asa sa ALS para makapag-aral ulit.” (FGD participant 6, lines 586-587)

The realization of having hope in ALS is to be able to study again.

“Ito ay nagpapadama sa akin kung ano ang gusto kong kunin na kurso sa hinaharap.” (FGD Participant 7, lines 665)

It lets us know what course I want to take.

Promote ALS. The participants were making an effort to raise awareness of ALS. They now understood that ALS could aid more students in their position. Because it was so beneficial, they encouraged those in the same position as them to study in ALS. They organized community outreach programs and shared their personal success stories to inspire others. Their advocacy efforts included collaborating with local organizations to promote the benefits of ALS education. Through these initiatives, they hoped to create a supportive network that would help more students access the opportunities provided by ALS.

“Ang pinakamalamang na ipo-promote ko bilang learner ng ALS ay ang isang dating mag-aaral ng ALS na nakasuot na ng uniporme ng kaniyang permanenteng trabaho ngayon dahil nagawa niyang makapagtapos ng ALS Kahit anong hirap ng hamon sa buhay iyon ay ang aming kapitbahay.” (IDI Participant 2, lines 186-189)

The person I will promote as an ALS learner is a former ALS student now wearing the uniform of his permanent job because he could graduate from ALS no matter how difficult life's challenges were, and that is our neighbor.

“Ang nais kong itaguyod na imahe ng mga mag-aaral sa ALS ay ang kalidad ng edukasyon at ang kanilang passion sa pag-aaral at pagkuha ng bagong kaalaman.” (FGD Participant 3, lines 293-294)

To promote the image of a learner in ALS is the quality of education and passion for learning and gaining new knowledge.

“Ang pinakamalamang na ipo -promote ko na imahe ng isang mag -aaral sa ALS ay mag-aaral ng mabuti Kung hindi pa kayo makapag- aral noong mga bata pa kayo nandyan ang ALS na handang tumulong walang pinipiling edad matanda man o bata basta”t magsumikap kalang at mararating mo ang iyong pangarap.” (FGD Participant 5, lines 509-513)

The image I will likely promote as an ALS learner is to study hard. If we cannot study as a child, ALS is there to help regardless of age. As long as we work hard, we will reach our dream.

“Sasabihin kong kaming mga mag-aaral ng ALS ay masisipag kami at matyaga dahil nagagawa namin ang aming mga gawain sa bahay kahit kami ay nag-aral pa.” (FGD Participant 8, lines 748-750)

We, ALS learners, are hardworking and patient because we can do our homework even though we are still studying.

Be Vigilant. The ALS students now knew to be more attentive. They believed that health is wealth, so it was crucial to take precautions. They understood the importance of following the proper health protocols. This awareness led them to adopt healthier lifestyle practices and emphasize the need for regular health check-ups. Additionally, they became more proactive in sharing these health insights with their peers, fostering a community-wide commitment to well-being. The emphasis on health also contributed to their overall resilience and ability to navigate challenges effectively.

“Ang natuklasan ko sa panahon ng pandemya ay walang araw na hindi nakasuot ng mask, at saka palagi po tayong gumagamit

nng alcohol at iba pa.” (FGD Participant 2, lines 174-176)

Discovered that during the pandemic, there is not a single day without wearing a mask, and then we are always using alcohol.

“Sa tingin ko, ang mga intervention na ginawa namin bilang mga mag-aaral upang harapin ang mga hamong naranasan namin sa panahon ng pandemya ay patuloy na magpatuloy sa pag-aaral ng mga mag-aaral sa pamamagitan ng pagsunod sa mga protocols at maging mas mapagbantay habang tayo ay patuloy na nakikipaglaban sa mga global na suliranin.” (FGD Participant 3, lines 286-289)

The interventions we have made as learners address the challenges we encountered during this pandemic: to continue the learners' learning by following the protocols and to be more vigilant while we are still battling these global issues.

“Keep safe always, pag-aalaga sa sarili ay nangangahulugan na pag-aalaga sa kaligtasan ng kapwa tao.” (FGD participant 6, lines 575-576)

Keep safe always; taking care of ourselves means taking care of the safety of other people.

“Sundin ang mga health protocol dahil mayroon lamang tayong isang buhay, at kailangan nating protektahan ito laban sa COVID-19 pandemic.” (FGD Participant 8, lines 730-731)

Follow the health protocol because we only have one life and must protect it against the COVID-19 pandemic.

Discussion

This section summarizes the discussion, recommendations for future researchers, and concluding remarks.

There were three research questions in this study; for the first research question, seven significant themes emerged from the data collected on the challenges of ALS students amidst the pandemic; for the second research question, eight significant themes emerged from the data collected based on how they coped up with their challenges amidst pandemic; while ten themes emerged on what their reflections as ALS learners amidst pandemic; results showed that the participants had similar challenges, ways of coping, and reflect with the challenges.

Challenges faced by ALS students during the pandemic. Seven major themes emerged from the data collected on the challenges faced by ALS learners during the pandemic: Answering the Modules, Adjustment, Absence of Face-to-Face classes, Lack of Gadgets, Shyness, Retrieval of Modules, and Poor Internet Connection.

Answering the Module. Answering the modules was a significant challenge faced by ALS students during distance learning. Several emergent themes highlighted the specific difficulties they encountered in this aspect. First and foremost, ALS students struggled to answer the modules, needing help responding to the questions and completing the assigned tasks. Thus, it may have been due to the complexity of the content, unclear instructions, or unfamiliarity with the learning approach. Moreover, some ALS students needed help understanding the activities within the modules. The language used, the structure of the activities, or the level of abstraction may have presented challenges, making it hard for students to fully comprehend and engage with the learning materials.

As a result, they may need help to provide accurate answers. ALS students believed it would have been better if the teacher could explain the lessons in the modules. They yearned for more guidance and clarification from their teachers, as they believed direct explanations and clarifications would enhance their understanding of the content and improve their ability to answer the modules accurately. Furthermore, ALS students reported needing help understanding the questions posed in the modules. The questions' wording, phrasing, or structure may have needed clarification, leading to confusion and hindering their ability to respond appropriately.

This assumption parallels the study of Chavez and Tadena (2021), who stated that the language used in the modules can be too advanced or technical for some students, making it difficult for them to understand and provide accurate answers. Additionally, instructions within the modules could have been more precise and helped the students' ability to complete the tasks effectively. Moreover, the identified issues, such as vague or ambiguous wording, complex sentence structures, and unfamiliar vocabulary, contribute to the students' struggle to understand the questions. Furthermore, students accustomed to traditional face-to-face instruction found it challenging to adapt to the independent nature of module-based learning. They needed help with self-directed learning and required additional support and guidance to engage with the modules effectively.

Adjustment. ALS students found the transition to the new learning format quite challenging, as it required adjustment to remote education, online platforms, and independent study methods. Navigating these changes and effectively engaging with online learning materials posed significant hurdles. Furthermore, ALS students struggled to adjust to the pandemic, dealing with increased stress, anxiety, and feelings of isolation, which hindered their ability to focus on their studies. Additionally, the lack of instructional materials compounded ALS students' challenges. Their skills to grasp concepts and complete assignments were improved with access to necessary textbooks, modules, or supplementary resources. Educational institutions and stakeholders needed to address these challenges by providing accessible learning resources, technological support, and emotional assistance to enable ALS students to thrive in the new learning landscape.

This assumption parallels the study of Asare et al. (2021), who found that ALS students experienced difficulties transitioning from traditional face-to-face classes to remote learning. They needed help with technological aspects, such as using online platforms and accessing digital learning resources. The shift to independent study methods and the absence of in-person interactions were significant challenges for ALS students in adjusting to the "new normal" learning environment. Additionally, students faced increased stress, anxiety, and feelings of isolation, which affected their ability to adapt to the new learning environment. The uncertainties surrounding the pandemic, disruptions to their daily routines, and the absence of social support structures contributed to these emotional challenges.

Absence of Face-to-Face Classes. The theme related to the absence of face-to-face classes encountered by ALS students highlights the challenges encountered during distance learning. ALS students need help obtaining modules due to transportation problems, which limit their access to necessary learning materials. They expressed that having face-to-face classes would have been preferable, as it would ensure timely access to modules and materials. Additionally, ALS students accustomed to face-to-face classes need help answering the modules. The absence of in-person interactions and immediate teacher guidance challenges comprehending the modules and completing tasks independently. They needed more teacher support and peer collaboration, as the absence of face-to-face classes meant no one was readily available to help them with the modules.

This assumption parallels the study of Dapar (2019), who revealed that ALS students accustomed to face-to-face classes encountered difficulties adapting to the new learning environment. Significant challenges were the need for in-person interactions, immediate teacher guidance, and peer collaboration. ALS students needed help comprehending the content independently and more support navigating the modules without the guidance readily available in face-to-face classrooms.

Gadget. The theme related to ALS students' challenges due to a lack of gadgets highlights the significant obstacles in their learning journey. ALS students experience falling behind their peers due to a lack of access to gadgets, which restricts their ability to receive essential information from the school. With devices such as smartphones or computers, they can stay updated with announcements, assignments, and instructional materials, putting them at a disadvantage. Additionally, ALS students may need more knowledge and skills to use innovative gadgets effectively. They need help navigating and utilizing devices like tablets, which fully hampers their ability to engage with digital learning resources. Moreover, the limited functionality of their gadgets can impede their ability to answer online activities that require research. ALS students found it challenging to gather information and complete assignments due to the limitations of their devices.

This assumption parallels the study of Caringal-Agum et al. (2020), who revealed that ALS students fell behind their peers due to the unavailability of gadgets such as smartphones or computers. The absence of these devices limited their access to essential information, resulting in a sense of disconnection from the learning process and potential disadvantages in receiving timely updates, assignments, and instructional materials. Additionally, the absence of proper training and guidance on using these technologies hindered their ability to fully engage with digital learning resources and take advantage of the learning opportunities provided by innovative gadgets.

Shyness. The theme related to the challenges of shyness faced by ALS students sheds light on the emotional barriers they encountered in their educational pursuits. ALS students experience shyness in various aspects of their learning journey, influencing their participation and sense of belonging. Firstly, they feel shy about being left behind by their classmates, comparing their progress and achievements to others. This self-consciousness and fear of falling behind contribute to feelings of inadequacy and hinder their social and academic interactions.

Additionally, ALS students may hesitate to enroll in educational programs due to their age, feeling self-conscious about being older than their peers and doubting their fit within the traditional educational system. Despite their shyness, ALS students also feel thankful for the opportunity to continue their studies through the ALS program. They expressed gratitude for the support and resources provided to them, recognizing the significance of this chance for personal and educational growth.

This assumption parallels the study of Labarrete (2021), who found that ALS students often felt shy and self-conscious when they perceived themselves to be falling behind their peers. They compared their progress and achievements to those of others, leading to feelings of shyness and reduced self-confidence in social or academic settings. Additionally, ALS students may feel shy and hesitant to enroll in educational programs due to their age. They may experience self-consciousness about being older than their peers or doubt their fit within the traditional educational system. These feelings of shyness and self-doubt can act as barriers to pursuing their educational goals.

Retrieval of Modules. The theme related to the challenges faced by ALS students in retrieving modules shed light on the significant obstacles they encounter in accessing the necessary learning materials. ALS students faced various difficulties in retrieving modules, impacting their educational progress. Firstly, ALS students find it hard to get the modules at school due to health issues, which may restrict their ability to go to school and collect the modules physically. These health concerns, whether chronic or temporary, limit their mobility and pose challenges in accessing the modules directly from the school premises.

Additionally, ALS students residing in far-flung areas needed help retrieving the modules due to the geographical distance from educational institutions. Travel time, limited transportation options, and logistical challenges pose barriers to physically accessing the modules from the school. Moreover, the unavailability of transportation further complicates the retrieval process for ALS students, as they rely on public or school-provided transportation that may be lacking or insufficient. This lack of transportation options hindered

their ability to retrieve the modules quickly. The difficulties retrieving the modules impact ALS students, causing sadness and frustration. They understand the importance of these learning materials for their education and feel disappointed when they cannot access them.

This assumption parallels the study of Kawinkoonlasate (2020), who revealed that ALS students in remote or isolated areas encountered difficulties accessing educational institutions due to geographical distance. Travel time, lack of transportation options, and logistical challenges posed barriers to physically retrieving the modules from the school premises. Additionally, the unavailability of transportation options created challenges for ALS students accessing the modules. Limited transportation services or lack of reliable transportation hindered their ability to retrieve the modules on time, impacting their educational progress.

Poor Internet Connection. The theme related to the challenges of poor internet connection faced by ALS students highlights the significant obstacles they encounter in accessing online learning resources. ALS students with poor internet connection face several emergent themes that impede their learning experience. Firstly, some ALS students need a better internet connection, resulting in their inability to complete assigned tasks. Slow or unreliable internet connections hinder their access to online learning platforms, making it difficult to upload or download files and submit assignments on time. This limitation affects their academic performance and can lead to frustration and feelings of inadequacy. Furthermore, some ALS students need help connecting to the internet, preventing them from engaging in online classes, accessing learning materials, and engaging in digital activities. The lack of internet connection deprives them of the opportunities provided by online learning platforms, significantly hindering their educational progress.

ALS students with unstable internet connections also need help attending online classes consistently. Their intermittent or unreliable internet connection disrupts their ability to join virtual classrooms, actively participate in discussions, and collaborate with peers. This instability creates barriers to their learning experience, leading to disconnection from their peers and teachers. Moreover, ALS students need an internet connection to stay updated with important announcements, updates, and curriculum changes. They need internet access to access online platforms where such information is shared, potentially creating a knowledge gap and hindering their ability to stay informed.

This assumption parallels the study of Labarrete (2019), who revealed that ALS students with inadequate internet connectivity faced difficulties accessing online learning platforms, leading to incomplete tasks. Slow or unreliable connections hindered their ability to download or submit assignments, impacting their academic performance and causing frustration. Additionally, students need help connecting to the internet, which deprives them of online learning opportunities. The absence of internet access prevented them from participating in online classes, accessing learning materials, and engaging in digital activities, significantly hindering their educational progress.

Coping Mechanisms of ALS Students with the Challenges They Have Encountered. Eight significant themes emerged from the data collected on how they coped with the challenges as ALS learners: being confident, firm, thinking positively, having faith, being independent, motivating oneself, asking for help, and making family and inspiration.

Being Confident. The coping mechanisms exhibited by ALS students in dealing with the challenges they encountered reflect their confidence. These students approach difficulties wholeheartedly, demonstrating a proactive and determined attitude in finding solutions and taking necessary actions to overcome obstacles. With confidence and inner peace, they handle challenges calmly, focusing on the task and approaching difficulties with self-assurance. ALS students draw inspiration from their parents, who serve as role models of resilience and guidance, empowering them to navigate challenges confidently. Holding on to their dreams and aspirations, ALS learners find the motivation to face challenges head-on, recognizing the importance of education in achieving their goals. They approach challenges, understanding that overcoming them is essential for personal growth and a fulfilling life. This confident mindset enables ALS students to develop effective coping strategies and adapt to adversity.

This assumption parallels the study of Lingad (2019), who found that ALS students exhibit a whole-hearted approach to dealing with challenges, demonstrating a proactive mindset. They actively engage in problem-solving, seek support from peers and educators, and take necessary actions to overcome obstacles. Also, highlighted the confidence and inner peace displayed by ALS students as they tackle difficulties. They remain composed, maintain a positive outlook, and approach challenges with self-assurance, allowing them to navigate obstacles more effectively.

Being Firm and Strong. The coping mechanisms exhibited by ALS students in dealing with the challenges they encountered reflect their remarkable firmness and strength, especially in the face of the pandemic. ALS students demonstrate resilience and determination as they navigate through the unique challenges brought about by the pandemic. They remain unwavering in their commitment to overcome obstacles and continue their educational journey, exhibiting a solid and committed mindset. Despite their difficulties, ALS students exhibit bravery and maintain a positive attitude, refusing to be deterred by setbacks or adversity. Their driving force is their strong desire to succeed in life, recognizing that overcoming challenges is crucial for achieving their dreams and creating a better future. ALS students actively employ coping strategies, seek support from their peers and mentors, and remain focused on their goals, allowing them to stay firm in facing difficulties.

This assumption parallels the study of Nonong (2022), who found that ALS students exhibit firmness and strength in facing challenges. They demonstrated resilience and determination in navigating obstacles, refusing to be deterred by difficulties, and maintaining a

steadfast attitude in pursuing their educational goals. The study also highlighted the bravery and persistence exhibited by ALS students as they persevered despite their difficulties. They demonstrated a tenacious spirit and maintained their commitment to achieving success.

Thinking Positively. The coping mechanisms exhibited by ALS students in dealing with the challenges they encountered reflect their optimistic mindset. ALS students approach difficulties with the belief that everything happens for a reason, embracing a positive perspective on life's challenges. They maintain positive self-talk, reminding themselves to stay positive and believe in their ability to overcome obstacles. This self-affirmation fosters confidence and determination, empowering them to surpass their challenges. ALS students understand the significance of a positive outlook in surviving and thriving amidst difficulties, choosing to focus on the positives and finding growth opportunities even in challenging circumstances. They firmly believe in their capability to succeed and confront the challenges posed by the pandemic with unwavering confidence.

This assumption parallels Pablo's study (2021), which found that ALS students maintain a positive mindset and exhibit resilience in the face of challenges. They approach difficulties with an optimistic perspective, recognizing the power of positive thinking in overcoming obstacles and adapting to changing circumstances. Additionally, having positive self-talk and believing in one's ability to overcome difficulties is essential. ALS students engage in affirmations and self-encouragement, fostering a sense of confidence and determination to face challenges head-on.

Having Faith. The coping mechanisms exhibited by ALS students in dealing with the challenges they encountered reflect their reliance on faith. ALS students drew strength from prayer and maintain a determined attitude as they navigate the challenges brought about by the pandemic. Their faith is a source of resilience and motivation, allowing them to persevere despite their difficulties. They firmly believe in their ability to confront life's challenges and maintain a positive outlook, knowing that with their determination and faith, they can overcome any obstacles that come their way. Moreover, ALS students find support and solace in the belief that others have in their abilities. Surrounding themselves with individuals who believe in their potential, they seek encouragement and assistance, which plays a significant role in helping them cope with their challenges.

This assumption parallels the study of Reyes (2021), who highlighted the role of faith in shaping their beliefs and maintaining a positive perspective. ALS students hold onto their faith, firmly believing that they can face and overcome the challenges in life, which fosters a sense of positivity and resilience. Also, students find comfort and strength in the support of others who share their faith. Surrounding themselves with individuals who believed in their abilities and provided encouragement and assistance.

Being Independent. The coping mechanisms exhibited by ALS students in dealing with the challenges they encountered reflect their value for independence. ALS students recognize the importance of being self-reliant in answering their modules and taking responsibility for their education. They understand that being independent is essential for their growth and success. Additionally, ALS students develop a sense of self-determination as they learn to stand alone and fight for their dreams. They refuse to let obstacles hinder their progress and persevere with unwavering determination. ALS students face challenges independently, believing in their potential, displaying confidence in their abilities, and finding innovative solutions. Moreover, ALS students demonstrate a high level of responsibility, not only in their academic tasks but also in managing household chores. They understand the need to balance school-related activities with daily responsibilities, showcasing a solid work ethic and discipline.

This assumption parallels the study of those who found that students value the essence of being independent in their learning process. They recognized the importance of taking responsibility for their education, including answering modules and engaging in self-directed learning. Independence in learning empowers them to navigate challenges and foster personal growth. Also, students develop a sense of self-determination and learn to stand alone in pursuing their dreams. They demonstrate resilience and perseverance, refusing to let challenges hinder their progress.

Motivating oneself. The coping mechanisms exhibited by ALS students in dealing with the challenges they encountered reflect their ability to motivate themselves. ALS students demonstrated remarkable self-motivation, continuously inspiring themselves to persevere and overcome obstacles. They understand the importance of their determination and resilience in navigating difficulties and staying motivated. Setting their sights on achieving their dreams, ALS students commit themselves to doing their best. They remain focused on their goals, using their aspirations as a motivation to push through challenges and hardships.

Additionally, ALS students firmly believed in the transformative power of the ALS program to help them eradicate poverty. They see this educational opportunity as a means to break free from their current circumstances and improve their lives. This belief is a driving energy, motivating them to persevere through challenges and make the most of their educational journey.

Moreover, ALS students maintained a strong sense of responsibility towards their families. They continually remind themselves that they can support and assist their loved ones when they graduate. This deep sense of familial duty and the desire to uplift their families is a powerful motivator, driving ALS students to overcome challenges and succeed academically. This assumption parallels the study of Ruiz et al. (2019), who found that students exhibit self-motivation and perseverance in navigating challenges. They possess an intrinsic drive to succeed and overcome obstacles, continually inspiring themselves to keep pushing forward. Also, students set specific goals and remain focused on achieving them, using their dreams and aspirations to motivate them to overcome challenges.

Asking for Help. The coping mechanisms exhibited by ALS students in dealing with the challenges they encountered reflect their willingness to ask for help. ALS students demonstrated a proactive approach in seeking assistance when they encountered difficulties answering the module or understanding its content. They understand the value of seeking support and guidance to overcome obstacles and deepen their comprehension. By asking for help, ALS students create a collaborative learning atmosphere where they can actively engage with their siblings, cousins, classmates, and parents. They appreciate the assistance they receive and feel a sense of happiness and relief knowing that they can rely on others for support. By asking for help, ALS students seek solutions to their challenges and foster meaningful connections with those around them.

This assumption parallels the study of Tarkar (2020), whose students recognized the value of reaching out for assistance when faced with challenges. They sought help from peers, family members, and teachers to overcome difficulties and enhance their learning experience. In addition, students seeking help from their social network experienced higher academic success. They engaged in collaborative learning environments and actively sought assistance from their families.

Making Family an Inspiration. The coping mechanisms exhibited by ALS students in dealing with the challenges they encountered reflect their ability to draw inspiration from their families. ALS students demonstrated a strong drive to overcome challenges and persevere because of their families. They understand that their family's support and well-being are closely tied to their success, motivating them to strive harder and find ways to navigate difficulties. ALS students approached challenges with a deep sense of responsibility toward their families, recognizing that their personal growth and achievements can positively impact their family's lives. This understanding fuels their determination to face challenges and give their best effort. ALS students draw inspiration from their family members as role models and sources of strength, and the support and encouragement they receive are powerful motivators to keep pushing forward.

This assumption parallels the study of Bacal et al. (2021), who found inspiration and motivation in their family members, who served as a source of strength and encouragement. Their love and care for their family members became a powerful motivator, fueling their determination to succeed and providing a sense of purpose in their educational journey. Also, saw their family's well-being and success as intertwined with their own, which served as a driving force to overcome challenges and achieve their goals.

Reflections of ALS Students Amidst Pandemic. Ten significant themes emerge from the data collected on the reflections of ALS learners amidst the pandemic: Essence of Hope, Value advantages, Identify disadvantages, Self-growth discovery, Achieve Educational Success, Be persistent, Effort matters, Great Impact of ALS, Promote ALS, and Be Vigilant.

Essence of Hope. The reflections of ALS students amidst the pandemic underscored the powerful essence of hope that permeates their experiences. Despite the adversities brought about by the pandemic, ALS students believed in the possibility of better days ahead. They find solace and inspiration in the ALS program, viewing it as a beacon of hope that provides them with educational opportunities and support during these challenging times. With an unwavering sense of determination, ALS students remain hopeful that they can complete their studies and achieve their goals. They recognize the ALS program as an avenue to pursue their dreams and a valuable opportunity to acquire knowledge, skills, and qualifications. ALS students firmly believe that nothing is impossible in achieving their dreams, even in the face of adversity, and they eagerly share their reflections and advice with others.

This assumption parallels the study of Chavez and Tadena (2021), who stated that students who maintained a sense of hope and optimism were found to have excellent levels of resilience, enabling them to navigate challenges and persist in their educational journey. Students who maintained a hopeful outlook were likelier to persevere through challenges and work towards their goals. They possessed a sense of hope that fueled their determination to succeed.

Value Advantages. The reflections of ALS students amidst the pandemic revealed their deep appreciation for the advantages offered by the ALS program. Despite the challenges posed by the new typical learning environment, ALS students have recognized and valued the unique benefits of studying in ALS. They express a profound sense of happiness and fulfillment in being able to continue their education through ALS, even in the face of the difficulties brought about by the pandemic. The program's flexibility has allowed them to successfully balance their studies with their work responsibilities at home, enabling them to juggle multiple commitments effectively. ALS students were grateful for the opportunity to continue their studies because of ALS, realizing that not all learners have the same access to education during these trying times. They feel privileged to have the chance to answer the modules provided by the program, recognizing the effort and resources invested in developing these valuable learning materials.

This assumption parallels the study of Gildo et al. (2023), whose students appreciated the opportunity to continue their studies while managing other responsibilities, such as work or family obligations, at home. The program's flexibility allowed them to adapt their learning to fit their circumstances. Additionally, the study revealed a sense of gratitude among ALS students for the opportunity to continue their studies because of ALS. They expressed appreciation for the support and resources provided by the program, recognizing the value of access to education during the pandemic.

Identify Disadvantages. The reflections of ALS students amidst the pandemic shed light on the disadvantages they have encountered in their educational journey. Some ALS students expressed sadness and disappointment as they could not continue their studies due to the pandemic's impact. The absence of a teacher or mentor to guide them through their lessons caused worry and concern as they grappled with the challenges of learning independently. Studying alone has proven difficult, as ALS students recognize the value of

collaborative learning and the support of peers and teachers. Additionally, some students still feel sad and frustrated because they struggle to fully grasp and understand the lessons even when they can access module answers. These reflections highlight the need for additional support mechanisms, alternative modes of instruction, and opportunities for collaborative learning to address the disadvantages of ALS students.

This assumption parallels the study of San Miguel and Pascual (2021), who revealed that the pandemic had led to a significant disruption in education, with ALS students facing challenges in continuing their studies. The inability to resume classes as planned has caused sadness and frustration among ALS students. Additionally, students needed help accessing guidance and instruction due to the absence of a classroom setting and face-to-face interaction with teachers. The lack of a teacher to teach and guide them through the lessons led to feelings of worry and uncertainty.

Self-Growth Discovery. The reflections of ALS students amidst the pandemic revealed their remarkable self-growth discoveries. ALS students discovered they possess the capacity to help and support other students striving to continue their education. This newfound role as mentors and guides brings them a sense of purpose and fulfillment as they realize the impact they could have on others' educational journeys. Furthermore, ALS students have discovered they can excel in their studies and achieve remarkable data. Through their experiences during the pandemic, they have witnessed their progress, growth, and improvement in studying and learning, which has boosted their confidence and motivation. ALS students have also learned to prioritize their health and well-being, recognizing the significance of self-care practices in supporting their educational pursuits. They had discovered the value of maintaining a balanced lifestyle, managing stress, and seeking support when needed.

This assumption parallels the study of Treceñe (2022), who found that ALS students experienced remarkable personal growth and discovered their potential for academic success. They recognized their capabilities and witnessed improvements in their studying and learning abilities, which enhanced their confidence and motivation. It also highlighted the self-discovery of ALS students in recognizing the importance of self-care practices and maintaining a balanced lifestyle. They learned to prioritize their physical and mental health, understanding that it directly impacts their educational pursuits.

Active Educational Success. The reflections of ALS students amidst the pandemic highlight their firm determination to pursue their dreams and achieve educational success. Despite the challenges posed by the pandemic, ALS students exhibited an unwavering eagerness to forge ahead and create a brighter future for themselves. They have realized the importance of education in attaining their goals and aspirations, which fuels their motivation and drive to excel academically. The pandemic has instilled in them a deeper appreciation for the value of education, recognizing it as a pathway to personal and professional growth. With this newfound perspective, ALS students diligently engage with their studies, putting forth their best efforts to answer the modules and complete their coursework. They were driven by the desire to graduate and secure better job opportunities.

This assumption parallels the study of Symaco and Bustos (2022), who revealed that ALS students are strongly determined to pursue their dreams despite the challenges. They showcased resilience and an unwavering commitment to continuing their education and achieving their goals. The study found that ALS students recognized the significance of education in securing a brighter future. They were driven by the understanding that education opens doors to opportunities and is crucial in improving their prospects for a successful and fulfilling life.

Be Persistent. The reflections of ALS students amidst the pandemic revealed their deep understanding of the importance of persistence. They realized persistence was necessary to navigate their challenges and achieve their goals. ALS students firmly believed that persistence and hard work were critical factors in surpassing the difficulties brought on by the pandemic. They had experienced firsthand the positive impact of persistence in handling their obstacles and difficulties, as it helps them develop resilience and find alternative solutions. ALS students value persistence because they aspire to become successful individuals and recognize that achieving their dreams requires a steadfast commitment to overcoming challenges. In their studies, they learned to be persistent in answering their modules despite the disruptions caused by the pandemic.

This assumption parallels the study of Diokno (2021), who revealed that ALS students recognized the importance of persistence in overcoming challenges. They understood that persistence and hard work were essential to navigate difficulties and achieve their educational goals. Also, the study found that ALS students attributed their ability to persevere in adversity to their strong sense of determination. They acknowledged that persistence was crucial for them to remain focused and motivated in pursuing their studies.

Effort Matters. The reflections of ALS students amidst the pandemic were centered around the belief that putting forth their best effort is paramount. ALS students recognized the significance of giving their best in all aspects of their lives, particularly during these challenging times. They understood that doing nothing would lead to failure and were determined to avoid such an outcome. Despite the difficulties brought about by the pandemic, ALS students were committed to their studies and were willing to work hard to achieve their goals. They realized that by giving their best effort, they can effectively face any challenges that come their way. This mindset reflects their resilience, determination, and proactive approach to their education. ALS students understand that their best effort is not only necessary for their academic success but also for their personal growth and development.

This assumption parallels the study of Fontanos et al. (2020), which revealed that ALS students recognized the importance of effort in achieving academic success. They understood that giving their best effort in their studies and other responsibilities was crucial for

overcoming challenges and attaining their goals. Also, the study found that ALS students attributed their ability to persevere and overcome obstacles to their strong sense of determination and their willingness to put forth maximum effort. They acknowledged that success was contingent upon their dedication and commitment to giving their best in their educational journey.

Significant Impact of ALS. The reflections of ALS students amidst the pandemic revealed the profound impact of the Alternative Learning System (ALS) on their lives. ALS students have come to value and appreciate the ALS program even more in the face of the pandemic. They expressed heartfelt gratitude for the chance to continue their studies through ALS despite the challenging circumstances. ALS had become a lifeline for these students, offering them an avenue to pursue their dreams and reignite their passion for learning. Through ALS, students have rediscovered their potential and realized they can achieve more than they initially believed. The program gave them the knowledge, skills, and support necessary to pursue their educational aspirations and accomplish remarkable feats.

This assumption parallels the study of Lau et al. (2020), who revealed that ALS students highly valued and appreciated the program, particularly during the pandemic. They expressed gratitude for being allowed to continue their studies through ALS and acknowledged the transformative impact it had on their educational journey. In addition, ALS students believed that the program provided them with a renewed sense of purpose and an avenue to pursue their dreams. They recognized that ALS opened doors to educational opportunities and rekindled their passion for learning.

Promote ALS. The reflections of ALS students amidst the pandemic highlighted their commitment to promoting the Alternative Learning System (ALS) and its benefits. ALS students actively advocated for the program, recognizing its value and impact on their lives. They go above and beyond to share their positive experiences with others and raise awareness about ALS as an effective educational option. ALS students have realized that ALS could help more students like them, offering an inclusive and accessible pathway to education. They understand the transformative power of ALS in providing educational opportunities, resources, and support that can positively impact students' academic and personal growth. With a deep belief in the effectiveness of ALS, they actively encouraged their peers to consider studying ALS, highlighting its helpfulness and the opportunities it provides.

This assumption parallels the study of Spencer et al. (2019), who found that students recognized the benefits of ALS and shared their positive experiences to inspire and encourage others to consider the program as an educational option. Additionally, the study revealed that ALS students played a significant role in recommending ALS to their friends and classmates. Their personal testimonials and advocacy efforts proved influential in raising awareness, generating interest in ALS, and showcasing how ALS students utilized various platforms such as social media, community events, and school assemblies to create awareness about ALS and its benefits.

Be Vigilant. The reflections of ALS students amidst the pandemic highlighted their heightened vigilance and recognition of the importance of health and safety. ALS students have become more mindful and cautious in their daily lives, taking proactive measures to protect themselves and others. They understand that health is wealth and prioritize their well-being by adhering to proper health protocols. The students have internalized the significance of practicing good hygiene, wearing masks, maintaining physical distancing, and following other preventive measures to prevent the spread of the virus.

This assumption parallels the study of Sugang and Cruz (2021), who found that students demonstrated a heightened vigilance towards health and safety measures, recognizing the importance of following protocols such as wearing masks, practicing physical distancing, and maintaining good hygiene. Additionally, students embraced a vigilant mindset, adapting to new health protocols and practices. They demonstrated a strong sense of responsibility in safeguarding their health and the health of others, showcasing their resilience and adaptability in navigating the challenges of the pandemic.

Conclusion

This research revealed numerous case phenomena regarding the obstacles faced by ALS students during the pandemic. The sleepless nights, intellectually draining days, financially depleted moments, physical weakness, and emotionally unstable sentiments experienced while completing this research were nothing compared to the revelations obtained after writing the manuscript. The findings of this study convinced us to accomplish anything, thanks to Allah, who provides us with power and bravery. I overcame all the challenges I faced while performing this research because Allah provided me with the tools needed to complete the study. My research adviser, the panel chair, members, and family have all assisted me in continuing and finishing this dissertation race. This study gave us a unique perspective that allowed us to fully understand the importance of conducting research.

References

- Almaiah, M. A., Al-Khasawneh, A., & Althunibat, A. (2020). Exploring the critical challenges and factors influencing the E-learning system usage during COVID-19 pandemic. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25, 5261-5280. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10639-020-10219-y>
- Ana, A., Minghat, A. D., Purnawarman, P., Saripudin, S., Muktiarni, M., Dwiyantri, V., & Mustakim, S. S. (2020). Students' perceptions of the twists and turns of E-learning in the midst of the Covid 19 outbreak. *Romanian Journal for Multidimensional Education/Revista Romaneasca pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/12.1sup2/242>

- Arnilla, A. K. (2021). Coaching teachers remotely during COVID-19 pandemic: Perspectives and experiences from a developing country. Available at SSRN 3873980. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3873980
- Arpilleda, D., & Jondy, M. (2018). Problems encountered by mobile teachers assigned in Tandag City Division, Surigao del Sur: A case study. *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences*, 3(5). https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3263400
- Asare, A. O., Yap, R., Truong, N., & Sarpong, E. O. (2021). The pandemic semesters: Examining public opinion regarding online learning amidst COVID-19. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 37(6), 1591-1605. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/jcal.12574>
- Baccal, V. S., & Ormilla, R. C. G. (2021). The implementation of Alternative Learning System in public schools in Isabela, Philippines. *EDUCATUM Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(1), 19-29. <https://ojs.upsi.edu.my/index.php/EJOSS/article/view/4082>
- Barrot, J. S., Llenares, I. I., & Del Rosario, L. S. (2021). Students' online learning challenges during the pandemic and how they cope with them: The case of the Philippines. *Education and information technologies*, 26(6), 7321-7338. <http://surl.li/dodmnn>
- Boeren, E. (2019). Understanding Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4 on "quality education" from micro, meso and macro perspectives. *International review of education*, 65, 277-294. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11159-019-09772-7>
- Busetto, L., Wick, W., & Gumbinger, C. (2020). How to use and assess qualitative research methods. *Neurological Research and Practice*, 2, 1-10. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s42466-020-00059-z>
- Can, Y., & Bardakci, S. (2022). Teachers' opinions on (urgent) distance education activities during the pandemic period. *Advances in Mobile Learning Educational Research*, 2(2), 351-374. <https://www.syncsci.com/journal/AMLER/article/view/AMLER.2022.02.005>
- Cardano, M. (2020). *Defending qualitative research: Design, analysis, and textualization*. Routledge. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/mono/10.4324/9780429464232/defending-qualitative-research-mario-cardano>
- Caringal-Agum, A. N., Baloyo, P. A., Juayno-Corpuz, J. M., Capobres, H. S., & Naidas, M. S. (2020). Students' perception of the use of the ICT in the Englas class of the Alternative Learning System: A case study. *Journal of Education, Psychology and Humanities*, 20. <https://ent.abs-cbn.com/itsshowtime/videos/tutti-caringal-joins-hide-and-sing-300392>
- Caulfield, J. (2019). How to do thematic analysis. <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=2746367>
- Chavez, M. B. B., & Tadena, L. Q. (2021). Alternative Learning System in time of COVID-19 Pandemic: Philippine Context. 14th La Salle Univ. Arts Congr, 5. <https://www.dlsu.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/pdf/conferences/arts-congress-proceedings/2021/sldp-03.pdf>
- Daher, M., Olivares, H., Carré, D., Jaramillo, A., & Tomicic, A. (2017). Experience and meaning in qualitative research: A conceptual review and a methodological device proposal. In *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung/Forum: Qualitative Social Research* (Vol. 18, No. 3, p. 24). DEU. <https://www.ssoar.info/ssoar/handle/document/58017>
- Dapar, M. M. (2019). The implementation of Alternative Learning System in Surigao del Sur Division. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*, 3(2M). <https://www.ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AJMRA/article/view/8466>
- Davis, T., Shemshack, A., & Kaymaz, M. (2020). Challenges k-12 schools have faced during COVID-19 distance learning. In *SITE Interactive Conference* (pp. 277-279). Association for the Advancement of Computing in Education (AACE). <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/218157/>
- Deterding, N. M., & Waters, M. C. (2021). Flexible coding of in-depth interviews: A twenty-first-century approach. *Sociological Methods & Research*, 50(2), 708-739. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0049124118799377>
- Diokno, M. S. I. (2021). Learning in a time of pandemic. COVID-19: Every woman's Feminist Response and Recovery Plan, 67. <http://surl.li/ksrbsh>
- Djalante, R., Nurhidayah, L., Van Minh, H., Phuong, N. T. N., Mahendradhata, Y., Trias, A., & Miller, M. A. (2020). COVID-19 and ASEAN responses: Comparative policy analysis. *Progress in Disaster Science*, 8, 100129. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2590061720300661>
- d'Orville, H. (2020). COVID-19 causes unprecedented educational disruption: Is there a road towards a new normal. *Prospects*, 49(1-2), 11-15. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11125-020-09475-0>
- Errasti-Ibarrondo, B., Jordán, J. A., Díez-Del-Corral, M. P., & Arantzamendi, M. (2019). van Manen's phenomenology of practice: How can it contribute to nursing. *Nursing Inquiry*, 26(1), e12259. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/nin.12259>
- Flaviano, R., Halili, R. A. E., Pojas, J. R., & Samosa, R. Pre-service teachers knowledge and attitude toward the implementation of Alternative Learning System: Input for Enhancement Training. <https://hcommons.org/item/hc:46355/>

- Fontanos, N., Gonzales, J. F., Lucasan, K., & Ocampo, D. S. (2020). Revisiting Flexible Learning Options (FLOs) in basic education in the Philippines: Implications for senior high school (SHS). UP CIDS Education Research Program. <http://surl.li/potlbq>
- Greening, N. (2019). Phenomenological research methodology. *Scientific Research Journal*, 7(5), 88-92. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Neville-Greening/publication/337106850_Phenomenological_Research_Methodology/links/620f3cefeb735c508add7902/Phenomenological-Research-Methodology.pdf
- Gildo, D. L., Bermundo, R. R., Rociento, M. M., Valencia, M. C., Eva, M. A., Barayoga, L. B., & Albero, I. (2023). School improvement and safety plan for limited face-to-face classes. *International Education Trend Issues*, 1(2), 88-97. <https://ijble.com/index.php/iети/article/view/152>
- Haven, L.T., & Van Grootel, D. L. (2019). Preregistering qualitative research. *Accountability in Research*, 26(3), 229-244. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/08989621.2019.1580147>
- Heng, K., & Sol, K. (2021). Online learning during COVID-19: Key challenges and suggestions to enhance effectiveness. *Cambodian Journal of Educational Research*, 1(1), 3-16. <http://surl.li/dadamz>
- Isidro, R. V., Oberio, R., & Petrola, J. P. J. (2022). Conquering the experiences of pain, boredom, and despair among selected incarcerated mothers through alternative learning system activities. *International Journal of Public Health*, 11(1), 303-309. <http://surl.li/wulxka>
- Jones, A. L., & Kessler, M. A. (2020, November). Teachers' emotion and identity work during a pandemic. In *Frontiers in Education* (Vol. 5, p. 583775). Frontiers Media SA. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feduc.2020.583775/full>
- Jolly, D. (2022). Impact of academic performance, personality types, self-efficacy and demographic profile to the employability skills of Alternative Learning System Learners. Personality types, self-efficacy and demographic profile to the employability skills of Alternative Learning System Learners (March 3, 2022). https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4048530
- Kawinkoonlasate, P. (2020). Online language learning for Thai EFL learners: An analysis of effective Alternative Learning Methods in response to the Covid-19 Outbreak. *English Language Teaching*, 13(12), 15-26. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1279886>
- Khosravi, H., Sadiq, S., & Gasevic, D. (2020, February). Development and adoption of an adaptive learning system: Reflections and lessons learned. In *Proceedings of the 51st ACM technical symposium on computer science education* (pp. 58-64). <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3328778.3366900>
- Knowles, M. S. (1968). *Andragogy, not pedagogy*. 1968. <http://surl.li/hrqzxp>
- Labarrete, R. A. (2021). Assessment for learning in the alternative learning system-education and skills training (ALS-EST). *ASSESSMENT*, 4(01). https://ijehss.com/uploads2021/EHS_4_213.pdf
- Labarrete, R. (2019). An assessment of Alternative Learning System-Accreditation and Equivalency (ALS-A&E) Curriculum for Secondary Clientele. *CNU-Journal of Higher Education*, 13, 43-55. <https://jhe.cnu.edu.ph/index.php/ojs3/article/view/12/4>
- Lapuz, M. C. L., & Pecajas, E. S. (2022). School heads' authority, accountability, and empowerment as functions of school performance. *International Journal of Novel Research in Humanity and Social Sciences*, 9(3), 69-83. <https://www.noveltyjournals.com/upload/paper/SCHOOL%20HEADS%20AUTHORITY-23062022-1.pdf>
- Lau, L. L., Hung, N., Go, D. J., Ferma, J., Choi, M., Dodd, W., & Wei, X. (2020). Knowledge, attitudes and practices of COVID-19 among income-poor households in the Philippines: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Global Health*, 10(1). <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7294392/>
- Larionova, M. (2020). The challenges of attaining the millennium development goals (MDGs). *International Organisations Research Journal*, 15(1), 155-176. <http://surl.li/rcfukd>
- Lee, Y. D., & Kuo, C. T. (2019). Principal's transformational leadership and teachers' work motivation: Evidence from elementary school in Taiwan. *International Journal of Organizational Innovation*, 1(3). <https://www.ijoi-online.org/attachments/article/114/0898%20Final.pdf>
- Le, K., & Nguyen, M. (2021). Education and political engagement. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 85, 102441. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0738059321000948>
- Lingad, J. (2019). Implementation of Alternative Learning System-Accreditation and equivalency among public secondary schools in Pampanga: Basis for strategic plan of action. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*, 3(8). <https://www.ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/3788>
- Maslow, A. H. (1943). A theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*, 50(4), 370. <https://www.excelcentre.net/TheoryHumanMotivation.pdf>

- Mazzucato, M., Kattel, R., & Ryan-Collins, J. (2020). Challenge-driven innovation policy: Towards a new policy toolkit. *Journal of Industry, Competition and Trade*, 20, 421-437. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10842-019-00329-w>
- Moleño, B. R. (2019). Influencing variables to the competencies of learners in the accreditation and equivalency test of alternative learning system. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports*, 6(3), 1-13. <http://archives.articleproms.com/id/eprint/677/>
- Mutch, C. (2021). 'Maslow before Bloom': Implementing a caring pedagogy during Covid-19. *Teachers' Work*, 18(2), 69-90. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1335080>
- Muzari, T., Shava, G. N., & Shonhiwa, S. (2022). Qualitative research paradigm, a key research design for educational researchers, processes, and procedures: A theoretical overview. *Indiana Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 14-20. [https://indianapublications.com/articles/IJHSS_3\(1\)_14-20_61f38990115064.95135470.pdf](https://indianapublications.com/articles/IJHSS_3(1)_14-20_61f38990115064.95135470.pdf)
- Nonong, E. G. (2022). Alternative Learning System program implementers' attitude and best practices: Basis for an enhanced development plan. <https://www.ijams-bbp.net/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/1-IJAMS-JUNE-ISSUE-378-394.pdf>
- Oducado, R. M., Rabacal, J., & Tamdang, K. (2021). Perceived stress due to COVID-19 pandemic among employed professional teachers. *International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation*, (15), 305-316. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3743860
- Osadcha, K., Osadchyi, V., Semerikov, S., Chemerys, H., & Chorna, A. (2020). The review of the adaptive learning systems for the formation of individual educational trajectory. *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*. <https://elibrary.kdpu.edu.ua/handle/123456789/4130>
- Pablo, J. C. (2021). Competencies of Alternative Learning System mobile teachers in schools division of Nueva Ecija. <https://www.ijams-bbp.net/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/IJAMS-OCTOBER-79-119.pdf>
- Pearse, N. (2019). An illustration of deductive analysis in qualitative research. In 18th European conference on research methodology for business and management studies (p. 264). <http://surl.li/mgylxe>
- Pliakos, K., Joo, S. H., Park, J. Y., Cornillie, F., Vens, C., & Van den Noortgate, W. (2019). Integrating machine learning into item response theory for addressing the cold start problem in adaptive learning systems. *Computers & Education*, 137, 91-103. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S036013151930096X>
- Pokhrel, S., & Chhetri, R. (2021). A literature review on impact of COVID-19 pandemic on teaching and learning. *Higher education for the future*, 8(1), 133-141. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/2347631120983481>
- Praveena, K. R., & Sasikumar, S. (2021). Application of Colaizzi's method of data analysis in phenomenological research. *Med Leg Updat*, 21(2), 914-8. <http://surl.li/aicnzo>
- Purnomo, E. P., Agustiyara, Nurmandi, A., Dewi, A., Rosa, E. M., Bayu, A. H., & Erviana, R. (2022). ASEAN policy responses to COVID-19 pandemic: Adaptation and experimentation policy: A study of ASEAN countries policy volatility for COVID-19 pandemic. *SAGE Open*, 12(1), 21582440221082145. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/21582440221082145>
- Quejada, A. B., & Orale, R. L. (2018). Lived experiences of elementary teachers in a remote school in Samar, Philippines. *Journal of Academic Research*, 3(3), 1-1. <http://surl.li/nrrawa>
- Qutoshi, S. B. (2018). Phenomenology: A philosophy and method of inquiry. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 5(1). <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1180603>
- Ravina, E. A. (2022). Service Learning (SL) in English language learning: The case of the Alternative Learning System (ALS) learners. *International Journal of Research*, 11(4), 9-19. <http://surl.li/kldinf>
- Reyes, R. T. (2021). Disparities, opportunities and Alternative Learning in the Philippines: A descriptive study of two Alternative Learning Systems for out-of-school youth. <https://archium.ateneo.edu/theses-dissertations/560/>
- Ribeiro, L. M., Cunha, R. S., Silva, M. C. A. E., Carvalho, M., & Vital, M. L. (2021). Parental involvement during pandemic times: Challenges and opportunities. *Education Sciences*, 11(6), 302. <https://www.mdpi.com/2227-7102/11/6/302>
- Rogers, C. R. (1983). *Freedom to Learn for the 80s*. Columbus, OH Charles E. Merrill Publishing Company. <https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=1055732>
- Ruiz, G., Pilapil, G. F., Rule, K. J. A., Tulod, S. A., & Amparado, M. A. (2019). Evaluation of the playgroup project and Alternative Learning System Programs in Village Looc and Village Opao, Mandaue City, Cebu, Philippines. *JPAIR Institutional Research*, 12(1), 23-39. <https://philair.ph/index.php/irj/article/view/742>
- Rutakumwa, R., Mugisha, J. O., Bernays, S., Kabunga, E., Tumwekwase, G., Mbonye, M., & Seeley, J. (2020). Conducting in-depth interviews with and without voice recorders: A comparative analysis. *Qualitative Research*, 20(5), 565-581. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/1468794119884806>

- Samat, M. F., Awang, N. A., Hussin, S. N. A., & Nawi, F. A. M. (2020). Online distance learning amidst COVID-19 Pandemic among university students: A practicality of partial least squares structural equation modelling approach. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 16(3), 220-233. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1274172>
- San Miguel, N. V., & Pascual, E. A. (2021). School leaders' resilience amidst pandemic in the division of Laguna, Philippines. *International Journal of Research Publications*, 88(1), 22-22. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342992348_Teachers'_Covid-19_Awareness_Distance_Learning_Education_Experiences_and_Perceptions_towards_Institutional_Readiness_and_Challenges
- Santos, J., De Jesus, L. F., Sealmooy, R. R., & Fajardo, R. R. C. (2021). Online distance learning amidst COVID-19. *IJERI: International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation*, (15), 291-304. <https://www.upo.es/revistas/index.php/IJERI/article/view/5271>
- Schweinsberg, M., Feldman, M., Staub, N., van den Akker, O. R., van Aert, R. C., Van Assen, M. A., & Schulte-Mecklenbeck, M. (2021). Same data, different conclusions: Radical dispersion in empirical results when independent analysts operationalize and test the same hypothesis. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 165, 228-249. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0749597821000200>
- Spencer, P. S., Lagrange, E., & Camu, W. (2019). ALS and environment: Clues from spatial clustering. *Revue Neurologique*, 175(10), 652-663. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0035378719306046>
- Sucgang, J. D., & Cruz, J. P. (2021). Philippine legal education in the time of pandemics. In proceedings of the 2021 12th international conference on e-education, e-business, e-management, and e-learning (pp. 187-194). <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3450148.3450154>
- Symaco, L. P., & Bustos, M. T. A. (2022). Overview of education in the Philippines. in international handbook on education in South East Asia (pp. 1-27). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-16-8136-3_1-2
- Tarkar, P. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on education system. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(9), 3812-3814. <http://surl.li/ulmjcj>
- Toquero, C. M. (2020). Emergency remote teaching amid COVID-19: The turning point. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(1), 185-188. <https://www.asianjde.com/ojs/index.php/AsianJDE/article/view/450>
- Talidong, K. J. B., & Toquero, C. M. D. (2020). Philippine teachers' practices to deal with anxiety amid COVID-19. *Journal of Loss and Trauma*, 25(6-7), 573-579. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/15325024.2020.1759225>
- Tindowen, D. J. C., Bassig, J. M., & Cagurangan, J. A. (2017). Twenty-First-Century skills of alternative learning system learners. *Sage Open*, 7(3), 2158244017726116. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/2158244017726116>
- Treceñe, J. K. D. (2022). COVID-19 and remote learning in the Philippine basic education system: Experiences of teachers, parents, and students. In socioeconomic inclusion during an era of online education (pp. 92-110). IGI Global. <https://www.igi-global.com/chapter/covid-19-and-remote-learning-in-the-philippine-basic-education-system/307359>
- Tria, J. Z. (2020). The COVID-19 pandemic through the lens of education in the Philippines: The new normal. *International Journal of Pedagogical Development and Lifelong Learning*, 1(1), 2-4. <http://surl.li/ftpyhc>
- Umanailo, M. C. B. (2019). Overview of phenomenological research. *Frenxiv Papers*, 1-6. <http://surl.li/paayrr>
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (2019). Combining data on out-of-school children, completion and learning to offer a more comprehensive view on SDG 4. <http://surl.li/xjmbcj>
- Vagle, M. D. (2018). *Crafting phenomenological research*. Routledge. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/mono/10.4324/9781315173474/crafting-phenomenological-research-mark-vagle>
- Van Manen, M. (2023). *Phenomenology of practice: Meaning-giving methods in phenomenological research and writing*. Taylor & Francis. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/mono/10.4324/9781003228073/phenomenology-practice-max-van-manen>
- Vatsalaswamy, P. (2020). Medical Education: COVID Journey. *Revista Argentina de Anatomía Clínica*, 12(3), 116-117. <https://revistas.unc.edu.ar/index.php/anatclinlar/article/view/30723>
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1987). *The collected works of LS Vygotsky: The fundamentals of defectology (Vol. 2)*. Springer Science & Business Media. <http://surl.li/xeadzv>
- Wang, X., Lei, S. M., Le, S., Yang, Y., Zhang, B., Yao, W., & Cheng, S. (2020). Bidirectional influence of the COVID-19 pandemic lockdowns on health behaviors and quality of life among Chinese adults. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(15), 5575. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/17/15/5575>
- Webb, A. S., & Welsh, A. J. (2019). Phenomenology as a methodology for scholarship of teaching and learning research. *Teaching and Learning Inquiry*, 7(1), 168-181. <https://journalhosting.ucalgary.ca/index.php/TLI/article/view/57538>

Williams, G. (2019). Applied qualitative research design. Scientific e-Resources. <http://surl.li/scmesv>

World Bank Group. (2018). A second chance to develop the human capital of out-of-school youth and adults: The Philippines Alternative Learning System. World Bank. <https://elibrary.worldbank.org/doi/abs/10.1596/30064>

Zhang, C., Ye, M., Fu, Y., Yang, M., Luo, F., Yuan, J., & Tao, Q. (2020). The psychological impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on teenagers in China. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 67(6), 747-755. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1054139X20305097>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Amillana Z. Kumpa

Dona Catalina Integrated School
Department of Education – Philippines

Jeannet E. Canda

Irineo L. Santiago National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Geraldine D. Rodriguez

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges – Philippines